

Next-generation of Energy Performance
Assessment and Certification

D7.4 Communication and dissemination activities final report

WP7 Project Outreach

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is providing an structured overview on the outreach results of the crossCert project related communication and dissemination activities. The report is a dossier of all the relevant dissemination and communication material developed from Month 18 to Month 36 of the Project. This report contains the summary of the communications and dissemination actions carried out and an assessment of the impact. Due to the adjustments to the D&C strategy (D7.1) following the SARS-COVID-19 Pandemic's impact on the target group's media consumer behaviour, some face to face activities were moved to the online space, thus we point out that the initial online operation of the project's communication and dissemination actions had an impact on the final project period as well. The main change included the extensive online event activities, reduction of press activities (since events where press could have been present did not take place) and focus on stakeholder engagement.

Dissemination and communication activities combined with stakeholder engagement activities reached **107823 external stakeholders**. Direct reach of project target groups via stakeholder engagement events, targeted newsletters and participation at relevant events reached **11711** stakeholders, with **993** Building Owners, **70** representatives of Certification bodies, **716** representatives of Energy Agencies, **877** Energy Auditors **1186** EPC Issuers, **382** representatives of Financing providers, **1213** Professionals in the construction sector, **2872** Representatives of Public authorities, **1665** Researchers, Researchers and **1737** representatives of Sectoral associations

Work Package 7 activities were dedicated to dissemination and communication, as well as the exploitation of results. The work in WP7 prepares the consortium's exploitation of the project results and supports the application and improvement of results by the stakeholders. All partners contribute to the work of WP7.

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Communication Dissemination Materials and Channels

Following the Project communication and dissemination plan (D7.1, submitted), the Communication and Dissemination Interim Report (D7.2) was summarising the main activities to maximise project impact and engage with relevant stakeholders. The project's visual identity including the project logo, further developed into the visual identity demonstrated in the Visual Identity Guide, various templates for PowerPoint documents as well as the project promotional materials (rollup, flyer, posters) along with the newsletter and website as well as social media channels have been already reported in detail in the Interim report (D7.2).

Visual Identity and dissemination materials

The developed promotional materials follow the project's Style Guide, included in D7.1 Communication and dissemination strategy. The project [Rollup](#), [Logo](#) and [Flyer](#) designed are available only for public download [via the project website](#). Furthermore in the second period of the project the following materials were developed by project partners:

Poster by University of Zaragoza

[Poster presented at WSED\(link\)](#)

Using the building certification methodology of another country: What have we learned?

Antonio Gómez, Norberto Fueyo, Ramón Chordá
 Aragon Institute for Engineering Research (I3A) – University of Zaragoza
 María de Luna 3, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain – Contact: antgomez@unizar.es

Towards reliable, practical, and people-centred European energy performance certification of buildings.

Objectives

CrossCert is committed to contributing to the success of the next-generation Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) by developing and testing guidelines and recommendations that aim to achieve the following:

- ✓ Improved accuracy and usability of the certificate.
- ✓ A people-centric design and a satisfactory user experience.
- ✓ Increased homogeneity across Europe.

CrossCert will provide Improvements and recommendations in all dimensions related to energy certification, which are classified as follows:

- Technical dimension.
- Human factor.
- Added value of energy certification (and connection with other instruments and tools).
- Harmonization of methodologies across Europe.

Methodology

Cross-testing involves calculating the energy performance of buildings using partners' national EPC calculation software. As a result of this exercise, we obtained an energy certificate for a building using the methodology of the country where that building is located (Home EPC), and another energy certificate applying the methodology of another country (Visiting EPC).

The results and the experience of using other EPC methodologies were compared, determining the differences between each certification procedure and the best practices applied in each country.

The methodology was applied to 140 buildings provided by crossCert partners. Several practical obstacles had to be overcome. These obstacles included widely varying climate conditions across countries (in most EPC software programs, it is not possible to import data for the climate prevailing at locations in other countries), language differences in EPC requirements, and differences in data requirements.

To overcome these obstacles, partners with similar climate conditions were identified and paired for cross-testing, while data requirements were compared and standardised.

The map shows how countries were paired according to climatic similarities and the buildings of other countries (Visiting EPCs) that each country has tested with its national methodology.

Results

Great variety of methodologies and input data

Energy certification methodologies used for buildings across Europe vary significantly. Each EPC method has different input data requirements or evaluations. For instance, in some countries, drawings are necessary, while this is not the case in others, or some countries evaluate lighting in the EPC, while others do not.

The approaches and hypotheses used to model elements and technical systems of the building also differ in each country. For instance, thermal bridges, user behaviour (occupancy, occupancy schedule, set point temperature, ventilation), U-values, or internal gains are generally determined differently in each country.

Consistent results despite the variety of approaches

There is a certain level of variation observed in the energy demand for heating (left) of the same building when methodologies from different countries are used.

On the other hand, a good correspondence is observed between the ratings (letters) obtained with different methodologies (right). The chart numbers represent how often the home and visiting country labels agree.

This consistency is relevant for the establishment of common policies across Europe on the energy renovation of buildings or a common scale in energy certification.

Performance gap causes

We have identified the reasons for the performance gap: the difference between the actual energy consumption in the building and the energy consumption determined by the energy certificates. We have classified the causes into two categories: those inherent to the certification methodology (blue balloons) and those due to the poor application of the methodology (orange balloons).

Knowledge Exchange Centre

Web-based repository of information on next generation EPCs

The Knowledge Exchange Center <https://crosscert.unizar.es/> is a web platform that facilitates the sharing of research articles, projects, and legislation on energy certification for buildings in a structured manner. Additionally, the platform includes a building data repository that developers and researchers can use to test software that calculates the energy performance of buildings.

More results on our website <https://www.crosscert.eu/>. Stay tuned for more results!

www.crosscert.eu

@PCrosscert

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Infographics developed by IRI-UL(WP5)

Developed as part of WP5 workplan, [detailed information and download available on the crossCert website \(link\)](#).

Event banners and social media images developed by Climate Alliance

Visualising Building Energy Performance

crossCert Focus Group
 Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification in the framework of the Grafting Cities Conference

19 October 2023
 17:00 - 19:00 CET
 Camera di Commercio
 Modena, Italy

crossCert is funded by EU's Horizon 2020 programme
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VISUALISING BUILDING ENERGY PERFORMANCE

crossCert
 Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

FOCUS GROUP

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme.

EPC RECAST **crossCert** **iBRoad2EPC** **EUB SuperHub**

THE NEXT GENERATION ENERGY PERFORMANCE CERTIFICATES CONFERENCE **EPBD RECAST EDITION**

23 MAY 2024
Mundo Madou, Brussels
and online

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THE NEXT GENERATION ENERGY PERFORMANCE CERTIFICATES CONFERENCE EPBD RECAST EDITION

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UPDATING EPCS FOR NEW CHALLENGES

crossCert WEBINAR
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

13th of July 2023
15:00-16:00 CEST

Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?

crossCert is funded by EU's Horizon 2020 programme GA 101033778. Views are our own

10:30-12:00 CET
27. 02. 2024
Tuesday

Are subsidies and public funding for renovations fit to speed up renovations?
How do energy certificates contribute?

Funding Options for Energy-efficient Building Renovations Across Europe

A crossCert Webinar
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

This project have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme.

10:30-12:00 CET
27. 02. 2024
Tuesday

Jana Lange
Efficiency in Buildings Officer
Franco-German Office for Energy Transition

Funding Options for Energy-efficient Building Renovations Across Europe

A crossCert Webinar
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

This project have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme.

10:30-12:00 CET
27. 02. 2024
Tuesday

Register now:
www.crosscert.eu

Funding Options for Energy-efficient Building Renovations Across Europe

A crossCert Webinar
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

This project have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme.

**DESIGNING THE PERFECT EPC:
WHAT WORKS FOR YOU?**

crossCert WEBINAR
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

**Wednesday
20. March 2024
9:30-12:30 CET**

crossCert is funded by EU's Horizon 2020 programme GA 101033778. Views are our own

**Designing the Perfect EPC:
What works for you?**

crossCert
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

WEBINAR

This project have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme.

ONLINE EVENT

New perspectives for impactful communication campaigns on energy-efficient renovations

Climate Alliance International Conference 2024

A crossCert WEBINAR
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

Energy Performance Assessment and Certification of Buildings

The future of EPCs

crossCert
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

FINAL WEBINAR

This project have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme.

Final Publishable Report developed by Climate Alliance

The full report was created by Work Package Leads guided by the project Coordinator. The Report then was designed by the graphic designer originally hired for the designing the visual identity of the project, commissioned by Climate Alliance. The full report is published on the project website. This report was launched during the final webinar of the project. It can be downloaded from the project website (<https://www.crosscert.eu/>) by [following the this link](#) or scanning this QR Code:

Excerpts from the report:

in to the newsletter list as well to receive information around new publications, project news and related services.

Climate Alliance has written, edited and sent six Newsletters and six Special Issue. The last regular issue was sent **to 68 Direct Subscribers, 74 Energy Agencies**, the special issue was sent **additionally to 90 Stakeholders** who registered to the Next-Gen EPC EU level Event. Overall, crossCert Newsletters reached **24467** stakeholders directly, while crossCert news in partner newsletters reached **4564** Stakeholders, including subscribers of the AEA and CA newsletters and the Bulgarian Municipal Energy Efficiency Network EcoEnergy Network Newsletter. Sister Projects have been invited before each newsletter to provide information, articles, news or events to be included.

Newsletter articles are available on full length via the [crossCert Website](#).

crossCert Newsletter			
No.	Content	No. of recipients	Date
1	crossCert Newsletter 1 - People-centred EPCs	97	29.03.2022
2	crossCert Newsletter 2 - People-centred EPCs	134	03.11.2022
3	Energy Efficient Buildings: Next Gen EPCs Event	90	08.07.2022
4	Recordings and Presentations: Next Gen EPCs Event	90	08.11.2022
5	crossCert Newsletter 3 - People-centred EPCs	64	28.02.2023
6	Webinars Special Issue	227	27.06.2023
7	crossCert Newsletter 4 - People-centred EPCs	140	04.10.2023
8	Upcoming Webinars on Funding and Design of EPCs		13.02.2024
9	crossCert Newsletter 5 - People-centred EPCs	230	09.04.2024
10	crossCert Newsletter 6 - People-centred EPCs	232	25.07.2024
11	Online Workshop: Registration Open: Webinars Special Issue	231	05.03.2024
12	Final Conference Special Issues (2 Calls)	232	22.04.2024
crossCert in Partner Newsletters			
1	crossCert Newsletter 2_AEA	101	31.01.2023
2	CrossCert SCM in Luxemburg and brief information about results from cross-testing of Bulgarian buildings	730	03.10.2022
3	Climate Alliance eClimail: Municipal practical experience with energy performance certificates in buildings wanted	3113	15.02.2022
4	Climate Alliance eClimail: August Feature: Promoting climate justice at the local level	3113	15.08.2022
5	crossCert Newsletter 3_AEA	96	04 2023
6	crossCert Newsletter 4_AEA	96	02 2024
7	crossCert Newsletter 5_AEA	96	04.2024
	Climate Alliance eClimail		
8	Promoting the webinar: "Funding options for energy-efficient building renovations across Europe"	3566	02.2024
9	Promoting "Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates conference"	3620	04.2024
10	Promoting the final crossCert webinar "Energy Performance Assessment and Certification of Buildings"	3733	10.2024

Newsletter Outreach

The Newsletter subscriber list counts **233 subscribers** as of 19. 11. 2024 consisting of a mix of crossCert stakeholder groups. All Newsletters were sent directly to subscribers in digital versions via e-mailing and are available to access online in separate landing pages. All together project newsletters reached cca. **23000 stakeholders**, including newsletters of partners and non-project related newsletters as well as the online version of the newsletter. A short analysis with the outreach figures can be found below. By analysing the figure in the first half of the project, we increasingly found that online traffic and newsletter subscriptions increase around events and stakeholder engagement activities, Thus it is not surprising, that instead of direct mailing subscriptions, stakeholders were focused more on online content and thus a high reach of online Newsletter versions was recorded. The online version of the newsletters were increasingly visited over 2023-2024.

Evidences: Direct links to online project Newsletters of the second project period

M18-36 Newsletter online versions:

[Third Newsletter](#)

[Fourth Newsletter](#)

[Fifth Newsletter](#)

[Sixth Newsletter](#)

Special Editions:

[Join our Webinar 1](#)

[Join our Webinar 2](#)

[Join our Webinar 3](#)

[Policy Conference Special](#)

[Policy Conference Programme Available](#)

[Final Webinar Invite](#)

Website

<https://www.crosscert.eu/>

The project website is rich in content, with sections dedicated to News and Events, Our Solutions. Resources include all event materials, infographics and videos as well as presentations related. Scientific publications and reports can be found in submenus that are interconnected. The Knowledge Center submenu leads the visitors to UNIZAR's external exploitation site. The articles of the Newsletters are posted on the website with direct links from the digital newsletters, allowing to elaborate on specific topics in a longer format. Direct links to social media are visible in the header, while the Sign-up form for the newsletter is visible in the Footer of the website, allowing also continuous visibility.

Website Outreach Statistics

The project website is tracked via the Matomo web analytics tool. The website attracted **3367 active users**. With actions on the website, most of the **9153 page views** were recorded on the landing page, then engaging the users for over **4,1 minutes** on average, with documents downloading counting **718 downloads, mostly Deliverables and Scientific results**. With the highest visitors' peak around the time of the events and research result releases, most visitors are interested in materials, followed by news and solutions.

Dissemination Videos and Short Video Clips

Videos produced as short ad clips for hybrid of online events and recordings of webinars

Next-Gen EPC Cluster Event 2022 Introduction:
[Energy Efficient Buildings: Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates - Welcome](#)

Next-Gen EPC Cluster Event 2022
 Minimum Energy Performance Standards in Buildings on the Ground - Julien Dijol
[Minimum Energy Performance Standards in Buildings on the Ground - Julien Dijol](#)

Next-Gen EPC Cluster Event 2022
 How to Make Next-Gen EPCs Meaningful for Consumers - Guillaume Joly
[How to Make Next-Gen EPCs Meaningful for Consumers - Guillaume Joly](#)

Updating EPCs for new challenges: Do EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD? - Webinar recording

[Updating EPCs for new challenges: Do EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?](#)

New perspectives for impactful communication campaigns on energy efficient renovations - crossCert webinar in the framework of CAIC 2024

[New perspectives for impactful communication campaigns on energy efficient renovations - crossCert](#)

Webinar: Online Workshop Ad clip - Designing the Perfect EPC

[Online Workshop: Designing the Perfect EPC](#)

Final Webinar Video Clip
[Join the crossCert final webinar!](#)

Final Webinar Recording

[crossCert Energy Performance Assessment and Certification of Buildings: The future of EPCs](#)

Communication activities and public engagement

Online Activities via Partner Websites and Blogs

Partner Websites

Several partner websites list crossCert related activities with link to the project website, thus directing traffic and interest towards the project results:

Weblinks	Language	Partners	Clicks/Views
crossCert @ AEA Website	DE	AEA	
Information/registry about first national stakeholder engagement event	DE	AEA	
Review of the first national stakeholder engagement event	DE	AEA	
Review of the joint webinar with sister projects (14.06.2022)	DE	AEA	
https://www.klimabuendnis.org/events/events/events-detail/energieeffiziente-gebaeude-energieausweise-der-naechsten-generation.html	DE	CA	70
https://www.climatealliance.org/events/events/events-detail/energy-efficient-buildings-next-generation-energy-performance-certificates.html	EN	CA	43
https://gfn.unizar.es/portfolio-items/crosscert/	EN	UNIZAR	
https://archive.newsletter2go.com/?n2g=ka648rqf-kwxvbf1-67k	DE	CA	278
https://archive.newsletter2go.com/?n2g=ka648rqf-iy5u9ysl-9w2	EN	CA	174
General CrossCert Website on CA Homepage in english	EN	CA	25
General CrossCert Website on CA Homepage in German	DE	CA	66
General CrossCert Website on CRES Homepage in Greek	GR	CRES	74
General CrossCert Website on CRES Homepage in english	EN	CRES	51
Post about crossCert meeting in Zaragoza	SI	IRI UL	
Post about crossCert meeting in Zaragoza	EN	IRI UL	
General Project Info	ES	EREN	
ETP and H+C Zero Network Webinar			
Post about EU projects that EREN is participating	ES	EREN	
Post about crossCert's webinar: Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?	ES	EREN	
General info about crossCert + documents	ES	EREN	
General info about crossCert	DK	EC Network	
Post about Training for executions of energy audits	SI	IRI UL	
Article about the event Towards a new generation of EPCs in Sofia and online	BG	EnEffect	

Announce of online crossCERT webinars	BG	EnEffect	
General info about crossCert, documents, news	PL	KAPE	
A website post - promotion of crossCert infographics	SL	IRI UL	
Events news about crossCert webinar	EN	CA	26
Event news	EN	CA	8

Social Media Strategy Outreach

It is almost impossible to do without a social media presence. Young people in particular use them to find out about current topics, events and trends and to exchange ideas. More than three quarters of all companies are already active on social media. Platforms such as Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, TikTok and LinkedIn offer numerous functions and different ways of communicating. Social media provides a cost-effective, fast and flexible way to reach a broad target group, promote transparency and build trust with supporters. They enable direct exchange, regular updates and increased engagement, regardless of geographical boundaries. However, using social media requires a lot of effort, especially when staff are limited. Constant adjustments to algorithms and trends are necessary. In addition, success is difficult to measure, as likes and shares often have no direct impact, and various platforms change their access strategy to measure post reach, like X did over the last 3 years after the takeover by Elon Musk (putting Statistics behind a paywall). Dependence on platforms entails risks: changes to algorithms and new terms of use can impair visibility. Data protection and the handling of supporter data are key, as is the risk of a loss of image due to inappropriate content. Another difficulty is standing out from the crowd. In addition, the lock-in effect makes it difficult to switch to other platforms.

When selecting platforms, the available resources were kept in mind for crossCert. Since it is usually more effective to use a few channels in a targeted manner rather than to use many only superficially, considering crossCert's target group, the ideal posting frequency, the preferred content and the available functions and features, the project channels chosen were LinkedIN, X and with less frequency, Facebook, focusing on events and publications as main content.

crossCert activities and project outcomes were distributed via social media, implementing the strategy of directing visitors to crossCert Materials and achievements on the website. Sister project events, stakeholder activities were also highlighted aiming to enhance multiplication effect. The originally planned project social media channels were enriched with a Youtube channel, given the change of event strategy due to the COVID-19 pandemic - since several events took place online, we decided to record presentations and make it available as extra content to our target groups.

While our X (Twitter) channel counts 90 followers, it used to be the most active channel by our target groups. However, since the last report, visibility of the channel changes due to algorithm adjustment, now resulting in **4449** (1552 impressions in the last 12 months, while it was resulting in 2897 impressions in the first part of the project with only 60 followers) impressions. The LinkedIn account with a following of 203 people has now become our most used channel resulting in **9292** Impressions (with 7134 impressions in the last 12 months before the project ended counted 2158 impressions in the first part of the project). Facebook remains very low with **448** (240 views in the last 12 months, while counted 208 in the first part of the project) while videos added on Youtube reached **305** views.

Facebook

- **users:** large, mixed target group; often from 25 years of age, local and global users
- **frequency of posts:** 3-5 times per week would be ideal, however crossCert results and events were not offering this high frequency, thus engagement via Facebook was given less emphasis.
- **content:** storytelling posts, community updates, events, infographics
- **features:** groups, events, stories, live videos, **page posts:** mostly Page Posts were used
- **opportunities:** use local topics and targeted group interactions to foster a sense of community: Partner Facebook channels posts were repost, giving more emphasis to local engagement.
- **Regularity:** Consistent posting times can increase visibility. Regular posts should be scheduled, thus Tuesday mornings and Thursday afternoons were used as posting times.
- **Algorithm:**
 - **Encourage interaction:** Facebook prioritises posts that have high interaction rates, such as comments and shares. It is advisable to create content that stimulates discussion or asks questions.
 - **Use video content:** Videos, especially live videos, are favoured by the algorithm because they often generate more engagement (interaction). Since crossCert did not produce any live videos, the visibility of Facebook posts plummeted and thus the Facebook follower base was not developed organically.

The Facebook Channel of the project was added to the originally planned two-channel strategy (Twitter and LinkedIn). The posts on Facebook engage the least.

X (formerly Twitter)

[crossCert Twitter/ X: 1552 Impressions last 12 months, 90 Followers](#)

- **Users:** news-oriented, politically and technically interested users worldwide, age group 18-49, a user group that correspond to crossCert Target group metrics
- **Frequency:** several times a day would have been ideal, however resources and results were not offering this frequency.
- **Content:** current news, opinions, discussions, threads and images were used in full disclosure
- **Features:** tweets, hashtags, images and short videos were exploited.
- **Opportunities:** up-to-date content, appealing hashtags, active discussion contributions and quick reactions were offered related to crossCert topics
- **Algorithm:** The algorithm favours current and trending topics. Relevant hashtags can be used to join current discussions. Short, concise tweets with a clear message achieve better results. Replies, retweets and likes increase the visibility of posts, thus the project's X account engaged in follower and relevant discussions.

The second best performing social media channel for **crossCert is X (Twitter)**. While it is the most volatile and quick-paced, it also provides the highest impression rates, as its hashtag tool efficiently creates a community of profiles active in the same fields, while also providing a tool for public awareness-raising on the same topic. In the case of our project, this is a very powerful characteristic.

LinkedIn

[crossCert LinkedIn: 7134 Impression last 12 months, 203 Followers](#)

- **users:** Professionals and specialists, B2B and industry contacts, a group that worked best for crossCert content
- **frequency:** 2-4 times per week would have been ideal, however due to resources and content availability, posts were offering this frequency only around events.
- **content:** Specialist articles, industry news, success stories were used
- **features:** Articles, groups, company profile was implemented
- **opportunities:** Specialist posts, valuable insights, professional dialogue and networking were exploited.
- **algorithm:**
 - Professional value: Posts with professional content and added value for the community are favoured, this crossCert engaged with sister projects, relevant building related organisations
 - Engagement in the first few hours: The algorithm rates early interactions positively. Therefore, timely engagement after publication was promoted.
 - Hashtags: Specific, professionally relevant hashtags were consistently used, but no more than three to five.

The most successful social media channel for crossCert has proven to be LinkedIn with **7134** Impressions on posts. With experts being active in the fields related to energy efficiency in buildings, this channel brings high interaction value. Looking into the statistics of impressions, the dynamics follow the dynamics of Twitter interactions, where events and result launches create most interest in time.

The metrics show several peaks: the Next-Gen EPC EU-level event and several posts related to newsletters and activities. At the same time Engagement statistics in LinkedIn show that engagement rates follow impressions, still content is key and that interactivity keeps engagement high also in times where impressions fall.

Youtube

The Project added **Youtube** to its originally planned social media channels as part of the mitigation strategy for events taking place online. The goal is to reach more stakeholders via recorded videos of events. These videos posted on the project's Channel reached **305** views since the creation of the channel.

Social Media on Partner Channels

PP	Topic	Post	Reach
CRES	connect prioritee project	https://www.linkedin.com/in/prioritee-plus-project-3405b5151/	187
CRES	retwitt at PrioritEE	https://twitter.com/PCrosscert/status/1471092879879725069	154
ENEFFECT	Information about the forum conducted. National event of crossCert project was conducted as a separate session.	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02tZbVSjot96zdLGmz4Xb2Y88KPNpfrGVobV256oEEb58rmxRcD2NoSXAsHk2NsYs1l	407
ENEFFECT	Roundtable about low carbon economy transition	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid032NvhU1iMoT8magCqvJaf61af20JT8HpzG7mzBsyksmXJRnLprh1K8KyxKYsZBrt5l	217
ENEFFECT	Information about <i>The Role of EPCs</i> event	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02H3g3YnMmPmYG8AzeT3CPN2JtdTyaSmbJf6PmfGT6MpoJqtYpR2XGtxRThLTZawcwI	280
ENEFFECT	Information about <i>The Role of EPCs</i> event	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0jJifc0nssLnY9C9SlvkCsRcuLADon3ZW6WTfDKVzKjgrKlJaW0hMoFvebXi2dc77l	337
ENEFFECT	Information about <i>The Role of EPCs</i> event	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6930048628065480704	95
ENEFFECT	International discussion forum "The future of smart buildings - concept, standards, good practices"	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6919930123202740225	48
IRI UL	Post about the first newsletter	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid02KXRCFkdUWVm353HnFafEXhLnV0cAy6ZsmS9g3oLEuNZBks66dN7N90EX7cuSavMel	22
IRI UL	Post about the first newsletter	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6915224206158774272	61
IRI UL	U-CERT & X-tendo final conference: enhanced and future-proof EPCs	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid0iAEWRFCRsULDk7B4fQcQAYjF71hbWKHPt95StcivqBsW6QDYqJF85jGGKQD4eFhtI	22

IRI UL	U-CERT & X-tendo final conference: enhanced and future-proof EPCs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6945002731094863872/	54
IRI UL	Energy Efficient Buildings: Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid0oSgWMX297PB7XFrKLN79C9GHkhf9pZ7C2vDLGWNFx0xVHCefowFov20Ni8KqgeydI	17
IRI UL	Energy Efficient Buildings: Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6975459355726888960/	70
IRI UL	2nd project newsletter	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid020AtMVbyZ9WHgnPLpF1JnMhMxHHfwqi1mgTtEuZXRxlMkA6sXGJPKTXxuVwawHpdI	18
IRI UL	2nd project newsletter	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7002912812247207936	88
CRES	connect with CRES' social accounts	https://twitter.com/CRES_HELLAS	75
CRES	connect with CRES' social accounts	https://www.facebook.com/kapecres?ref=tn_tnmn	2700
CRES	connect with CRES' social accounts	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cres/	7100
ECNET	crossCert deliverables	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid08jOK87ZqWSEmJYCTvT3YQWCVPNS2P7a9dSRxBn6wmUaRvCF4Z45WPVxAcE9oSiWDI&id=100063674995527	2670
ECNet	Post sharing LinkedIn	https://twitter.com/roundbaltic	345
ECNET	Sharing info on online communication event	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=470582159064649&set=a.130822769707258	
ECNET	Info on Next Generation EPC Conference	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7188891802123255808/	97
ECNET	Sharing crossCERT post on EPBD recast	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7200790124551409665	
ECNET	Info on final webinar	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7259141555586826241	152
ECNET	Sharing info on final webinar	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=546192074836990&set=a.130822769707258	65
ENEFFECT	Information about The Role of EPCs event	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6930048628065480704	106
ENEFFECT	Information about Leaders Who Build is the largest two-day interactive forum in architecture and construction.	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02HUU44XNyNcJJwYzhtftgjtJknvba8eggqs6a9pp5UWwWJtZMACzLLSPCG1AmCDfwkI	458
ENEFFECT	Post about Towards a new-generation EPCs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7024303848311664640	156

ENEFFECT	Post about Towards a new-generation EPCs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7024307139225526272	111
ENEFFECT	Information about Towards a new-generation EPCs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7026109593290223616	29
ENEFFECT	Information about Towards a new-generation EPCs	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0CtehnTFhA3FFUvCWdDCmZMSWK7RjH1c8x0aJiC1HKnu9L36R1rN8G10js6d4hdTKI	524
ENEFFECT	Information about Towards a new-generation EPCs	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0dJMhK3iaCxMeKDr87H9PB7Met4FTRWvA0WUdnAeB7Wl_x9F03bfRg2X9NbiBuyoyWI	356
ENEFFECT	Information about Towards a new-generation EPCs	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02qTczwRG4nUR4MHtWgZjYAzVdj1cYK0nsCUeheqv3rjJPqycH5z3AK07XSAD17ViVI	542
ENEFFECT	Information about Towards a new-generation EPCs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7029726292375744512	109
ENEFFECT	Recording from Towards new-generation EPCs event	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Or0YPh5Dh7U	38
ENEFFECT	Recording from last Towards new-generation EPCs	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0V4DteEmfvWti9ZCoxFRDvLVZ7Cr9ky8rpBBE8PfrKkMEkayIjX7h29oqUYHNPM5fl	131
ENEFFECT	Recording from last Towards new-generation EPCs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7031171313486475264	69
CA	crossCert Youtube channel	https://www.youtube.com/@projectcrosscert8054	76
CA	crossCert Twitter channel	https://twitter.com/PCrosscert	2897
CA	crossCert LinkedIN channel	https://www.linkedin.com/company/crosscert-project/	2158
CA	crossCert Facebook channel	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100083386058679&sk=about	206
IRI UL	Post about crossCert meeting in Zaragoza	https://twitter.com/iri_ul/status/1636002123845345280?s=20	25
IRI UL	Post about crossCert meeting in Zaragoza	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid0ergDov3zWpRepJoePFS5KTYcRpXnJPPRDuL_yBUuVvy1ERzLqNHPNB62EzRLoHCVbl	58
IRI UL	Post about 3rd newsletter	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid02qLrL5JS2MgGV2fn9Tb3PLbfsLAE66yC3FuY5pbUHFft9p2ARNq4qMhFisBMhGoTtl	30
IRI UL	Post about Webinar on 13th of July	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7080163416899751936	69
IRI UL	Post about Webinar on 13th of July	https://twitter.com/iri_ul/status/1674398418817495041?s=20	38
IRI UL	Post about Webinar on 13th of July	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid0vUR6KZd52GXpw540	23

		scG4emHrZEp6soxZSaYWPfcR6gScZdTiiKdEHE6iV6VK84GsI	
IRI UL	Post about 4th newsletter	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid0q2C7KRX1dBP7VojSvAyedHekejgcMvH1g9KYDdJj5c0GiLcvzZhj6RaqbHXJ3sV3l	
IRI UL	Post about 4th newsletter	https://www.linkedin.com/in/prioritee-plus-project-3405b5151/	115
CRES	Post about 4th newsletter	https://www.linkedin.com/in/prioritee-plus-project-3405b5151/	187
CRES	Post about 4th newsletter	https://twitter.com/Prioritee1	154
CRES	post about the survey	https://www.linkedin.com/in/prioritee-plus-project-3405b5151/	187
CRES	post about the survey	https://twitter.com/Prioritee1	154
CRES	Post about 4th newsletter	https://twitter.com/CRES_HELLAS	78
CRES	post about the survey	https://twitter.com/CRES_HELLAS	78
CRES	post about the survey	(20+) Facebook	2700
CRES	post about the survey	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cres/posts/?feedView=all	7100
CRES	Post about 4th newsletter	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cres/posts/?feedView=all	6672
EREN	Post about EU projects EREN is participating	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1752444156859822088?s=20	119
EREN	Post about the webinar: Funding Options for Energy-Efficient Building Renovations Across Europe	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1750602252069281898?s=20	47
EREN	Post about EREN in TIMEPAC 2023 workshop	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1742470697769721942?s=20	67
EREN	Post about EREN in TIMEPAC 2023 workshop	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1737436094638002640?s=20	53
EREN	Post about EREN in TIMEPAC 2023 workshop	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1737435499269071004?s=20	178
EREN	Post about HWU's survey	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1729216158346199466?s=20	67
EREN	Post asking for collaboration on HWU's survey	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1729216159625388525?s=20	48
EREN	Post about TIMEPAC 2023 Workshop: Towards a dynamic and enhanced EPC: advanced procedures for building assessment and certification	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1726688612526567860?s=20	71

EREN	Post about the Survey on "design and experience of EPCs"	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1706252820733698157?s=20	64
EREN	Post about general crossCert's general info	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1680825479496884224?s=20	104
EREN	Post about crossCert's webinar: Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1678684803225341954?s=20	99
EREN	Re-post about crossCert's webinar: Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?	https://x.com/PCrosscert/status/1678315124292046850?s=20	337
EREN	Post about crossCert's webinar: Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1678276865138753536?s=20	107
EREN	Post about crossCert's webinar: Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?	https://x.com/EnergiaJCyL/status/1676633681593614337?s=20	100
EREN	Re-post about crossCert's webinar: Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?	https://x.com/PCrosscert/status/1671847506010054658?s=20	587
EREN	Post about the webinar: Funding Options for Energy-Efficient Building Renovations Across Europe	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/energiajcyL_webinar-funding-options-for-energy-efficient-activity-7156270426837463040-ADTe?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	2
EREN	Post asking for collaboration on HWU's survey	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/energiajcyL_encuesta-dise%C3%B1o-y-experiencia-de-uso-de-activity-7134848731815755778-edhM?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	3
EREN	Post about TIMEPAC-2023 - Towards a Dynamic and Enhanced EPC (1st part)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XACwa0eqtGg	9
EREN	Post about TIMEPAC-2023 - Towards a Dynamic and Enhanced EPC (2nd part)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h3q5k6mYV1U	
EREN	Post about D4.2	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/energiajcyL_publicado-el-an%C3%A1lisis-de-la-integraci%C3%B3n-activity-7183372453748850688-IHKY?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	
EREN	Post about 2nd national stakeholder's conference	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/energiajcyL_conferencia-online-el-futuro-de-la-certificaci%C3%B3n-activity-7188106474798125056-2dMa?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	

EREN	Dissemination of SCM 6	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/energiacijl_durant-e-la-reuni%C3%B3n-de-trabajo-en-liubliana-activity-7173666343500595201-Xp2i?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	
CRES	Re-post about crossCert's webinar (27Feb 2024) and Workshop (20 March 2024)	https://twitter.com/Prioritee1	154
CRES	Re-post about crossCert's webinar (27Feb 2024) and Workshop (20 March 2024)	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7170760790675861504/	187
CRES	Re-post about crossCert's webinar (27Feb 2024) and Workshop (20 March 2024)	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100063191173168	182
CRES	Post about yje Workshop (20 March 2024)	http://www.cres.gr/cres/pages/news/news_ekdiloseis.html	105
IRI UL	Post The 6th crossCert Newsletter	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/iriul_crosscert-energycert-ene-rgyefficiency-epc-activity-7224045069018832897-S9X4?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	128
IRI UL	Post The 6th crossCert Newsletter	https://twitter.com/iri_ul/status/1818280168689135935	16
IRI UL	Conference announcing	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7188450434670350336	554
IRI UL	Conference announcing	https://twitter.com/iri_ul/status/1782686903377990064/photo/1	69
IRI UL	CrossCerrt consortium meeting in Slovenia - news	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7173993178591612928	1359
IRI UL	CrossCert webinar announcement - Designing the perfect EPC	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7173607877205602304	292
IRI UL	CrossCert webinar announcement - Designing the perfect EPC	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171035619349917696	180
IRI UL	Post webinar "Funding Options for Energy-Efficient Building Renovations Across Europe" invitation	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7162781424981270528	182
IRI UL	Re-post - 5th newsletter announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7183798235621146625	146
IRI UL	Post webinar "Funding Options for Energy-Efficient Building Renovations Across Europe" invitation	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/iriul_epcs-nextgen-epcs-energycert-ene-rgyefficiency-activity-7155857220075765760-W_WA?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	203
IRI UL	Post webinar "Funding Options for Energy-Efficient Building Renovations Across Europe" invitation	https://twitter.com/iri_ul/status/1750096905554608270/photo/1	16

ENEFFECT	Post announcing the upcoming event Towards a new generation EPCs in Sofia	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0dnJgd2GHUUHyr6NaVXi6o2jiiDBEJfkSjgRFUWiJWWhqUnTNoJa8KWckLbikL UqDoI	402
ENEFFECT	Post following the event	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02qNvsr2n3sJojXUDn6UzzNxzqYALmf49No1qaNYHpYHCky1AbD05Fpau9D6rRFdUuI	756
ENEFFECT	Post sharing a recording from the event	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0V9gmqzZPppVzMwSGPgJBPbv6pJHZVtzkswkaJgKBdqclV5dT6gYjGWHcnNwiemX9I	202
ENEFFECT	Post discussing SRI at a public conference organised by Ministry of Energy	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0A8moU1rLPE2bBCXY3iQP6mwqz6srgZbL0PHDEsM56gKftfoVmULwVW8U1CViKpsNI	226
ENEFFECT	Post from C4E where energy certificates were a topic of a specialized workshop session	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02Rn15jMt0aZRfb18t3710LbfG6hxSB5oYr2Lyy1pAl5vFs9S0M4v9Wq7sDh8WZVI	479
ENEFFECT	Sharing a survey on the design and experience of EPCs	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0vuTmr5pk4uWzjEf0JFca1G4o7GcUxhzzySsj3m7f2AL2F6RQ3XsbWN8pFhEucU8BI	160
ENEFFECT	Announcement of the upcoming XVII Annual Conference of the Association of Bulgarian Energy Agencies	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid028n2pRuRmSJhznEFUEji51sTMvoYsgrVFrL47khNb70JvCBDhV6tcyWBTim0uNoPVI	400
ENEFFECT	Post following the EPBD recast decision from 7 December 2023	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0333hq5xs0ydBhvG5FRhwRA7cvuMx3o7gw7yGl4Zy7PGvHBC1P1F6CeZCXTAZeEAfoI	95
ENEFFECT	Reminder of upcoming roundtable for financing of EE and RES investments in Sofia with the mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02sK65zAtbJgkc6NCE2xJVMBUAs8XhzPWpUoMiCjcrHqs7WTpWRridYJeXPuXsYs5Zl	306
ENEFFECT	Announcement of maximum room capacity at the public event from 30.01.24	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02etjo1Nf9nG5p0wvwoAJzL1FnSExye7UJ9r2CMroUchWTSk89GQX7qhc9tWgFvtNI	624
ENEFFECT	Invitation to the crossCERT webinar on 27.02	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0Yy4AnoQZdYXnNz26ioSTq1nEYk108mBrnnGKMAMGKXHJCabr5qGbJrymxaMDzLW3I	720
ENEFFECT	Invitation to crossCERT webinar on 20.03	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0FYRcKK6AVs4tyoVgh0DZRHp6F1YrKXAN7azRY1adPuVbPahbWHaq33osW9WBDrHzI	243
ENEFFECT	Announce of upcoming EcoEnergy conference	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0iFu3YmGaCuqrdKyXVvrSfssnRKcMi9ddpem21qdB8gStGBSskFs896bE7Xu3T8WhI	215
ENEFFECT	Announce of BeSMART final event with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0hw1CtU4Tm5rdPhRjL55rLp70uZG4f5aTdipMakZ3yMqfdhwDDaii7r1VFECzksBHI	390
ENEFFECT	Participants notification following the EcoEnergy conference	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0FC17jQxJtuBpPTot2CHXjBG1uC7uyK5fPRwxDEjJfZC4ddG9iB4gUJDHynk9uqhnI	185

ENEFFECT	Announce of upcoming EcoEnergy conference	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0N6oadCqC1dqzKre7zVth8F4pskNa5P7WvUHbHxYqByD9PrTPEkJN6EiZuTmoqHrfI	923
ENEFFECT	Announce of upcoming EcoEnergy conference	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02ePoEZfesm9VXJaNAvqgapXA1zL7oEUu28yVaejJFLBXLbNeu8VwN17AsMLLeCMHrI	150
ENEFFECT	Announce of an upcoming EBPD event with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02zvqsRxnzZMKcxoqt1nzF89o1NLDcwoy4Hwr3scjBiNt9c0uJzft2unr3qY5ddmHul	258
ENEFFECT	Announce of an upcoming EBPD event with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0nEfBR12MrUMWWJbmFM9UacbaNPiTpkoFVx8kLuNATHApcFGeLeU0AX3X5yCVLXR3I	162
ENEFFECT	Announcing the Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Days conference with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0qCmqHAR586Th8M5Kx0FKGsuD76EbVpDd6ahD9hrrvCP7TWKekiumP6eUSfw9aoDQI	362
ENEFFECT	Announcing the Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Days conference with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0kcdSpWCQXyqTHopAgKJ5S3Tqp3JfEXzPKnhb6a8fXAE6zYf547xuyfMrWb6eP1tUI	806
ENEFFECT	Announcing the Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Days conference with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02UN9MkFwDGPv4nFPdPJXbnyVmyCydU1BKr9MqmnBDe8YLCdy7kMuhMTjEeqj4VQbXI	506
ENEFFECT	Announcing the Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Days conference with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0hVELYdwefWo7VTT5D1p2obcc6u5iKrc2dZZfHZgiCDXPadsKAK10UNWvnm6bbYSFI	239
ENEFFECT	Announcing the Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Days conference with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02ZWizu7jwb56wn8NyPu6iC3F25hCjym330pxXXJkWBv1T0bemDM4xLBcoHpTu3qyZI	553
ENEFFECT	Announcing the Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Days conference with a mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0SYkuNfskykvuzU7LNftNy4ukPsbardNb8zGCV9EntXerct2rwotz3pD2fLrymJqBI	167
ENEFFECT	Post from the start of the EE and Green Energy Confernece and sessions announce	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0ZosYuPmpcbgu5Hs2r1kKAAnxHSfdc9GxAPvBL8NUXRfWCH7P9C0G9wt3FGpoCH2kl	504
ENEFFECT	Post from the start of the EE and Green Energy Confernece	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid02WNfwCWFjqS9Xjo5z77MKDwa40P6AaxKVowya4t7W5XmmnSsYEJDKeShP85Jb11FFyI	448
ENEFFECT	Post from the start of the EE and Green Energy Confernece	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0YcdgCuGi2YnjYedCDh8qQcbJVEJmJNf6rnWc5g2wXCfjFs9EHfJ8asZumCiRmRBTzI	909
ENEFFECT	Mayors Talk conference announce and mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid0i8UKWYwu5dFnGVPKw5q3r4uz0P5qDDTt63tGTfNJC2qffmyfKkU1K1wOX7Fn132NI	397

ENEFFECT	Mayors Talk conference post and mention of crossCERT	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/pfbid00xUWuR8CWrtPV99XzHCaGn2mWFHcJGryLuq2Azyos6eXmvqKCGoSfUrjD8VGnvWuI	171
ENEFFECT	Announce of the XVII Annual Conference of the Association of Bulgarian Energy Agencies via EcoEnergy	https://www.facebook.com/ecoenergybulgaria/post/pfbid0v9T6a0fZw9fd3E7L0kU2upxNFgdFYvoVVxnNGprzxqCLq6LcvKzdLSoG8DQt2vAEI	36
ENEFFECT	Announce of Mayors Talk via EcoEnergy	https://www.facebook.com/ecoenergybulgaria/post/pfbid0zoCY6zru1KfHZAiNG625SLxXW6tHS7iqYcn7tFTVPdB4cbfm2ehNN1S4vzz2CoPU	70
ENEFFECT	Announce of EPBD recast event with a mention of crossCERT via EcoEnergy	https://www.facebook.com/ecoenergybulgaria/post/pfbid0352hkccFCPVnyHC2vE0mAcXzCNwiudkEccRwVuuYqv0dPuDqaZvt777wVPf5qdTjv	55
ENEFFECT	Announce of BeSMART final event with a mention of crossCERT via EcoEnergy	https://www.facebook.com/ecoenergybulgaria/post/pfbid026fX6GHKwZ8wMYrUzmnMcwwrUd8Tu9D0YpBCYkVVjrfxq5H5vkorxMxSY6x76puI	104
ENEFFECT	Post following BeSMART final event via EcoEnergy	https://www.facebook.com/ecoenergybulgaria/post/pfbid0ZqQEGELfcTGVJpevEfiirtC3zroNrN8jyG5mqVJgMJd2dbyulpHU4bXe93yKzJzyl	88
ENEFFECT	EPBD recast event reminder via EcoEnergy	https://www.facebook.com/ecoenergybulgaria/post/pfbid02JzpnHz8SdCRmxHJYUf6tt35cn7w9BSVwwe8mobDKWeXWuNYMRkNoZ5JLHte78zX9I	207
ENEFFECT	EcoEnergy newsletter announce mentioning crossCert	https://www.facebook.com/ecoenergybulgaria/post/pfbid0248B3X7UfS7rMa5v1EkcFk4w2f79Yk7SjduoKSSLUAfKxX31Hj7x00z3tnkqcN7BFI	153
ENEFFECT	Announce of Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Days	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7199391858014216193	245
ENEFFECT	EPBD recast event reminder	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7196102835975970817	304
ENEFFECT	Post following BeSMART final event	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7188788409170087936	406
ENEFFECT	crossCERT webinar announce	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7163467987566465025	133
IRI UL	EPC Journey - INTRODUCTION POST	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7216339268187660288	459
IRI UL	EPC Journey - RISE AWARENESS	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7219944757861466113/	258
IRI UL	EPC Journey - ENGAGE (2)	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7219944757861466113/	290
IRI UL	EPC Journey - ARRANGE THE ASSESSMENT (3)	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7221386071127842817/	224
IRI UL	webinar	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/iriul_webinar-com-communication-energyefficiency-activity-7234112890897641472-G4ng?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	358
IRI UL	webinar	https://x.com/iri_ul/status/1828348448531243490	21

IRI UL	EPC Journey - GATHER DATA & INFORMATION	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7222110890509107200/	286
IRI UL	EPC Journey - PROCESS DATA & INFORMATION	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7223922901060583424/	169
IRI UL	EPC Journey - ISSUE & DELIVER EPCs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7224647605333446656/	145
IRI UL	EPC Journey - USE EPCs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7226459605617319936/	161
IRI UL	EPC Journey - REPEAT	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7227184330953920512/	235
IRI UL	Promotion of crossCert infographics	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/iriul_crosscert-crosscert-activity-7259121566548934659-j40j?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	200
IRI UL	Promotion of crossCert infographics	https://x.com/PCrosscert/status/1848632386004611550	9
IRI UL	Repost - crossCert newsletter	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid02uWEPdsAMdQpS2MtqAhJTM6cWsxylD8iLiOeKwk2jw8pUchg5nHPHaJXovAGFvgVNI	
IRI UL	Promotion of crossCert infographics	https://www.facebook.com/institute.for.innovation.and.development/posts/pfbid0kGN1PYfseMoAixiYuTYtL1Ax1P1Xoqfie1WHnW7rUXfaGtm22JhMDBJD2i7yx9al	3
IRI UL	Funding options webinar promo	https://x.com/iri_ul/status/1757020532514382001	21
CA	crossCert Youtube channel since interim	https://www.youtube.com/@projectcrosscert8054	223
CA	crossCert Twitter channel since interim	https://twitter.com/PCrosscert	1552
CA	crossCert LinkedIN channel since interim	https://www.linkedin.com/company/crosscert-project/	7134
CA	crossCert Facebook channel since interim	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100083386058679&sk=about	240
ENEFFECT	crossCERT final webinar announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eneffect-center-for-energy-efficiency_epc-energyperformance-future-ofbuildings-activity-7264251941432479745-_lyq	609
ENEFFECT	crossCERT final webinar announcement	https://www.facebook.com/eneffect/posts/58819122022785?ref=embed_post	174
CRES	crossCERT final webinar announcement	https://www.facebook.com/kapecres?ref=tn_tnmn	2700

Dissemination and Networking Activities

Networking and stakeholder engagement was taking place mostly on a national level with various joint events organised by all partners. Furthermore, UNIZAR and Climate Alliance participated in the joint activities of the Next-Gen EPC Cluster and contributed to joint events organised, and the activities related to the Horizon Booster activities. These sister project partnerships and joint communication efforts are particularly successful when jointly organised, the highlight of this joint effort were the [Next-Gen EPC EU level event](#), the [Focus Group Event](#) and the [Policy Conference](#) organised in the course of 3 years. Altogether 19 [Sister projects](#) and related research initiatives were involved in active collaboration via events, joint activities, by University of Zaragoza, Climate Alliance, the Austrian energy Agency, CRES and EREN including:

EUB SuperHub, European Building Sustainability performance and energy certification Hub

iBRoad2EPC, Integrating Building Renovation Passports into Energy Performance Certification schemes for a decarbonised building stock

TIMEPAC, Towards innovative methods for energy performance assessment and certification of buildings

QualDeEPC

X-tendo

ePANACEA

EPC RECAST

D2EPC

E-DYCE

U-CERT

PadovaFIT

EUROPA

outPHIT

TIMEPAC, Towards innovative methods for energy performance assessment and certification of buildings

x-Tendo

D^2EPC

QualDeEPC

SMARTREADY easySRI

Tunes

Altogether, 1495 stakeholders were directly involved in project dissemination (national stakeholder and EU level) events, **and more than 3600 stakeholders participated in crossCert events** or at events organised by external organisations where crossCert was presented directly, thanks to sister project collaborations and project activities with cross-testing activities.

Dissemination via stakeholder events served as the basis for dissemination of results. The Project Partners organised and co-organised **22** online and face-to-face events and presented at various conferences, and organised national engagement events. Furthermore, 6 international Webinars were organised by Climate Alliance. Main stakeholder engagement events with national focus included:

Event	No. of Participants	Date		Type	PP	Link
Austria: The next generation of EPCs - start webinar	64	31/5/2022	online	National Engagement Events	AEA	Anmeldeformular
Greece: Cross Cert National Workshop	19	1/6/2022	online	National Engagement Events	CRES	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/greece-1st-stakeholder-event
Bulgaria: crossCert: Bulgarian National Stakeholder Engagement Event	130	17/03/2022	hybrid	National Engagement Events	ENEFFECT	
Denmark and Poland Joint national event: RoundBaltic National stakeholder Engagement Event with X-tendo	38	6/23/2022	hybrid	National Engagement Events	ECNET KAPE	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/denmark-poland-the-roundbaltic-learning-event
Spain: crossCert: 1st Workshop Spanish Stakeholders	10	5/12/2022	presence	National Engagement Events	EREN	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/spain-1st-stakeholder-workshop
Malta: crossCert 1st Stakeholder Engagement Event	35	6/22/2022	presence	National Engagement Events	MIEMA	
Climate adaptation and resilience on the local and regional level - Croatian perspective	20	6/30/2022	presence	National Engagement Events	REGEA	https://resilience.eu/climate-adaptation-and-resilience-on-the-local-and-regional-level-croatian-perspective/
Energy Efficient Buildings: Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates: crossCert Next-Gen EU Level Event	99	28/9/2022	Luxembourg	crossCert EU Level Events	CA	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/nextgenepc-eu-level-event
Online Workshop: MAKING ENERGY PERFORMANCE VISIBLE - WG Buildings online event at CAIC'22	50	29/9/2022	online	Digital Networking Events	CA	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/digital-workshop-with-municipalities
Denmark: 2nd National Engagement Event (Info and Discussion Stand at two days national Conference)	32	05/03/2023	presence	National Engagement Events	ECNET	https://www.energiforumdanmark.dk/
2nd crossCert Webinar: Webinar: Upgrading EPCs for new challenges - Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?	81	13/07/2023	online	Digital Networking Events	CA	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/upgrading-epcs-for-new-challenges-do-all-eu-countries-have-to-pre

						pare-for-the-same-costs-of-the-epbd-1
Focus Group Meeting, Modena, Italy	21	10/19/2023	Modena	crossCert EU Level Events	CA	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/focus-group-event-visualising-building-energy-performance
Spain: crossCert: 2nd Workshop Spanish Stakeholders	357	25/04/2024	online	National Engagement Events	EREN	https://energia.jcyl.es/web/jcyl/Energia/es/Plantilla100Detalle/1262861836918/Evento/1285386161288/Comunicacion
Greece: Cross Cert National Workshop	7	20 Feb. 2024	online	National Engagement Events	CRES	
Bulgaria: Final National Stakeholder Engagement Event	76	30.5.2024	f2f	National Engagement Events	ENEFFECT	https://www.eneffect.bg/bg/news/1270/v-burgas-se-provezdat-dni-na-energiinata-efektivnost-i-zelenata-energiia
Webinar: Funding Options for Energy-Efficient Building Renovations Across Europe	76	2/27/2024	online	Digital Networking Events	CA	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/webinar-funding-options-for-energy-efficient-building-renovations
Workshop: Designing the Perfect EPC – What works for you?	79	3/20/2024	online	Digital Networking Events	HWU	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/webinar-designing-the-perfect-epc-what-works-for-you
Webinar: New perspectives for impactful communication campaigns on energy-efficient renovations	63	28/08/2024	online	Digital Networking Events	CA	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/webinar-new-perspectives-for-impactful-communication-campaigns-on-energy-efficient-renovations
Policy Conference: Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates Conference – EPBD Recast Edition	66	05/23/2024	Brussels	crossCert EU Level Events	CA	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/policy-conference
‘Energy Transformation – Challenges, Opportunities and Prospects’	74	10/16/2024	hybrid	National Engagement Events	KAPE	https://30lat.kape.gov.pl/
Final Webinar: Energy Performance Assessment and Certification of	174	21/11/2024	online	Digital Networking Events	CA	https://www.crosscert.eu/materials/events/webinar-ene

Buildings: The future of EPCs						rgy-performance-assessment-and-certification-of-buildings-the-future-of-epcs
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crossCert Stakeholder Engagement Events M18-36

The crossCert Stakeholder Engagement Event details for Month 1-18 can be found in D7.2 Communication and Dissemination Interim Report. The below summaries refer to events organised in the second reporting period, Month 18-Month 36 in reverse time order.

[From mandatory document to decision-making tool: the evolution of the energy performance certificate. - Austria: 2nd National Stakeholder Event](#)

On **November 26, 2024**, the Austrian Energy Agency (AEA) hosted the second national stakeholder feedback workshop titled 'From mandatory document to decision-making tool: the evolution of the energy performance certificate.' Held online, the event brought together 13 participants representing stakeholder groups like the scientific community, civil society, policymakers, investors, and customers.

The workshop focused on presenting the vision for the future of Austria’s energy performance certificate system, highlighting innovations aligned with the 2024 Energy Performance of Buildings Directive. Participants explored Austria-specific fields of action, examined challenges in creating user-friendly EPCs, and discussed structured approaches to achieve improvements.

Attendees gained a detailed understanding of the EPBD requirements and identified key challenges and opportunities for the Austrian context. They explored critical aspects of user-friendly EPC design and defined steps to improve the system within their own professional capacities.

Feedback from participants emphasized the value of the presented outcomes, with requests for concrete redesign proposals for the EPC. The Austrian Energy Agency committed to creating a new design based on workshop discussions and project recommendations, which will be shared with the OIB consortium for integration into national regulations.

The event successfully engaged representatives from Tyrol and Vorarlberg, who showed enthusiasm for incorporating the findings into regional frameworks. Despite initial caution toward regulatory changes, these representatives expressed a willingness to collaborate on future improvements.

Following the workshop, printed crossCert booklets were distributed to participants and other key stakeholders to support the application of the discussed solutions. The updated EPC design, reflecting the collective insights, is set to be submitted to the OIB consortium for adoption.

'Energy Transformation - Challenges, Opportunities and Prospects' - Poland: National Stakeholder Event

On 16 October 2024, a conference entitled 'Energy Transformation - Challenges, Opportunities and Prospects' was held in Warsaw. The event provided an excellent opportunity to promote key projects supporting sustainable energy and energy efficiency measures. KAPE's relevant projects were presented during the conference. In addition, nine projects supported the conference: ENSMOV PLUS, DEESME, KnowNebs, CrossCert, TunES, L2H, R4H, FEPC and Enerfirst.

Participation in panel discussions

Projects also actively participated in individual panel discussions, where experts discussed key challenges and opportunities related to the energy transition. Each project brought valuable information and experience on energy efficiency, renewable energy sources and innovative technological solutions that can contribute to climate goals.

The second conference panel, entitled 'Challenges for the buildings sector in the context of the Green Deal', will discuss the challenges faced by the public, commercial buildings sector in achieving the European Green Deal. We learned about the legal conditions the government is working on, we diagnosed the expectations of the building sector from financial institutions in terms of the EU Taxonomy, and we talked about solutions to bring buildings to a zero-emission standard.

Speakers on the panel were:

- Dariusz Koc - Director of the Department of Energy Efficiency and Energy Transformation, National Energy Conservation Agency
- Tomasz Gałązka - Adviser, Department of Low-Emission Economy, Ministry of Development and Technology
- Mariusz Sadłowski - Deputy Director, Department of Ecology and Energy, Head of Energy Department, Gdańsk Municipal Office
- Ilona Otoka - ESG Services Manager - Cushman & Wakefield
- Dorota Bartosz - Sustainable Construction Director, Polish Green Building Council PLGBC
- Janusz Czarnogórski - President of the Management Board, water supply and sewage company in Ząbki

The panel was supported by crossCert and Tunes projects. The Conference summary:

https://youtu.be/TwB5V2I-LPw?si=EYNkWH_ITvdX3NAE

The conference was an excellent opportunity to showcase projects that play a key role in the energy transition. Promotional activities, including posters and active participation in panel discussions, allowed a broad presentation of the benefits of

projects and the establishment of new contacts that will contribute to future cooperation in energy efficiency.

Promotional activities related to the project

As part of the promotion of the above projects, a range of information materials were prepared, including: posters, which were displayed in the conference venues, providing participants with easy access to information on each project.

Social media campaign: Regular news posts and live coverage published on platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook and Twitter. The campaign ranged from event announcements to speaker presentations and the conference programme.

Mailing to partners and industry target groups: Information about the conference was sent directly to partners and industry organisations involved in energy, green and sustainability, which helped to attract interested participants from the energy sector, industry and the public sector.

Articles in trade media: An outreach campaign was conducted in popular trade media such as magazines, online portals and specialised newsletters to reach experts and companies working in the field of energy transition. Media coverage and streaming: Media coverage was provided during the event and online streaming was provided for participants who were unable to attend stationary. (streaming: <https://www.youtube.com/live/pOIXtF1eF-s>)

Promotional materials: A dedicated section for the conference was created on the organiser's website, where a detailed programme, speaker profiles, information on panel topics and a registration form for participants were posted. (<https://30lat.kape.gov.pl/> - site has 8 575 visits). Printed promotional materials: Posters, flyers and roll-ups were prepared and strategically placed during the event.

Support from partners and institutions: Conference partners, industry organisations and academic institutions supported the promotion of the event through their own communication channels, increasing the reach of the promotion.

Online Workshop / [Webinar: Designing the Perfect EPC – What works for you?](#)

20. March 2024 09:30 - 12:30 CET | Digital Stakeholder Workshop - Webinar 3

Participant Download: EPC Feature Examples:
[EPC_feature_examples.pdf](#) 969 KB

Designing the Perfect EPC Presentation:
[Designing_the_perfect_EPC.pdf](#) 1 MB

This crossCert Webinar moderated by Prof David Jenkins, Professor of Energy and Buildings, Heriot-Watt University

Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) are a central part of energy efficiency legislation in buildings throughout Europe. Due to their extensive usage, they must inform a broad range of different user groups. Currently, EPCs are being reviewed and revised to support more challenging carbon targets across European countries – hence the concept of “next-generation” EPCs that may use new metrics and indicators to support various areas of decision-making.

The EU Horizon-funded [crossCert](#) project is attempting to test and critique many of these new approaches against the needs of different user groups. As part of this research, the team carried out a focus-group style event to engage with those that need EPCs to make decisions on low-carbon buildings. The event asked participants, in small groups, to indicate what type of EPC (and related information) would be most useful for them, understand whether current EPCs are meeting user requirements, and use this to guide design of future EPCs.

The online event also included an overview of crossCert and the latest research being undertaken to create next-generation EPCs that create maximum impact for the user. The event was of interest to anyone, across Europe, currently relying on EPCs to make informed decisions or are part of the EPC process itself. This includes: EPC assessors, those forming policy that use EPCs, building managers, large property owners, engineers, and designers/architects.

Agenda

9.30 AM	Welcome and introduction
9.40 AM	The crossCert project – an overview
10.00 AM	Introduction to activity
10.15 AM	Coffee break
10.25 AM	Choosing an EPC that works for you (Breakout session)
11.40 AM	Reporting back and comparing results
12.15 PM	Closing words and resume

[The Future of Energy Performance Certification of Buildings](#) **Spain: 2nd event for Spanish Stakeholders**

April 25, 2024

The Ente Regional de la Energía de Castilla y León, as an energy agency participating in the European project [Cross-Cert](#) (Improving the usability of energy performance certificates for buildings), organised a webinar on Energy Efficiency in Buildings on **25 April** from **10:00 to 11:45 a.m.** The event aimed to address current developments and challenges in energy efficiency in buildings, a topic of growing importance on the European and global scene .

The seminar was structured in five key sections, starting with a presentation on the new Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, presented by **Pau Garcia** representing the European Commission, during which an overview of the proposals and targets set out in the new directive, crucial for Europe's energy future, was given. Afterwards, **Antonio Gómez**, from the University of Zaragoza (UNIZAR), shared the results of the cross-testing of Building Energy Performance Certificates obtained. This presentation shed light on the importance of harmonisation and reliability of energy performance certificates at European level. **Adrián Fernández**, from the Ente Regional de la Energía de Castilla y León (EREN) focused on the integration of Building Energy Performance Certificates in databases and their valorisation, underlining the relevance of data management and exploitation to improve energy efficiency in buildings, and how it contributes to energy savings. The last presentation, by **Aitor Domínguez** from the Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (IDAE), emphasised the upcoming requirements for energy efficiency certification in Spain, anticipating the changes and challenges that the sector will face in the coming years. Finally, the event concluded with a round table discussion, moderated by **Alfredo Cadórniga** from EREN, on the future energy efficiency assessment of buildings and the new rating scales, where, in addition to the previous speakers, **Rafael Villar** from the Eduardo Torroja Institute of Construction Sciences of the CSIC participated. This debate offered a broad view on the future perspectives and challenges in the evaluation and qualification of energy efficiency in the field of buildings.

Days of energy efficiency and green energy - Bulgaria: Final National Stakeholder Engagement Event

The Final Stakeholder Engagement Event of the crossCERT project in Bulgaria was organized by EnEffect as a separate session on **May 31, 2024**, as part of a three-day [national conference](#) focused on green energy, knowledge, and education for energy efficiency and renewable energy sources (RES). This conference took place from May 30 to June 1 in Burgas, Bulgaria.

The session served as a training opportunity for municipal specialists, introducing them to new tools at the European level designed to support building renovations. Attendees also included representatives from the National Agency for Sustainable Energy Development, as well as companies specializing in energy audits of buildings. During the session, the project's main results were presented, highlighting potential improvements in national building certification schemes to enhance the quality and reliability of information relevant to building owners' needs.

Additionally, the event addressed new indicators for buildings, such as the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) and Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ), and introduced tools like the building renovation passport. An overview of the indirect benefits of energy renovations for buildings was also provided.

Main Takeaways

To achieve decarbonization of their building stock, Bulgarian municipalities must revise their existing building renovation practices and explore new financing methods for renovation projects, particularly in light of significantly reduced grant funding. The new generation of building energy performance certificates, along with the building renovation passport, are essential tools that must

ensure the quality and reliability of projects to secure financing from various sources and meet ambitious renovation goals.

In addition to the introduction of these tools, it is crucial to enhance the qualifications of energy auditors by implementing new periodic training programs focused on innovations in energy renovation and building certification. Finally, developing high-quality software for assessing the energy performance of buildings and automatically generating the necessary documentation is of utmost importance.

Project progress update and consultation regarding training on Energy Efficiency Certificates - Greece: Cross Cert National Workshop

20 Feb. 2024

The event aimed to inform engaged stakeholders in Greece on crossCert project progress and discuss with them views regarding training and education services for Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) issuers. Besides, to discuss the barriers and challenges the previous training on EPC in Greece faced and hear proposals for improvements in a possible new cycle.

Memo of the workshop discussions

E. Taxeri briefly presented the project progress....She referred to the results of the recording of existing training procedures in each country and its evaluation.....

Dr George Koras introduced the topics on which the discussion would be based. He referred to the existing situation regarding training on EPCs in Greece and he asked for the participants' views regarding the need for a new training course in Greece, the topics that should be included, its duration, etc. Then, a roundtable discussion took place leaving the floor to the invited stakeholders.

Firstly, D.M referred to the current quality of EPCs. He said that, in their great majority, they are not of satisfactory quality especially when it comes to small/medium residencies. The reasons behind could include lack of knowledge and time of the issuers. So, he considers that there is a great need for training. The courses should include the presentation and secure understanding of the existing regulatory framework as well as the software. Most of the issuers do not know how it works. Besides, they have to be informed about the latest developments in equipment.

Then, A.A from CRES (projects I-Tunes-....) said that while during the first years the information and training provided to energy inspector candidates was more than enough, the situation got bad when this became not obligatory and gets worse as time passes. He added that some professions, for example mechanical engineers, guarantee a level of relative knowledge some others do not and thus require additional and specialised training. The need is much more imperative now that additional requirements for buildings come in (SRI, etc.).

Furthermore, Mrs F.A., said that serious mistakes, made by EPC issuers, have been noticed. There is a serious lack of knowledge even regarding legislation. Besides, some of the issuers do not recheck to see

their results. Obligatory training is considered useful, it should include information on electromechanical systems and technical equipment specifications.

Mrs. M.P. from the Ministry of Environment and Energy, said that it is optimistic that educational institutions include more and more courses on energy efficiency and RES. She agrees that there is a lack of knowledge regarding EPCs software and the TOTEE (Technical Instructions of the Technical Chamber of Greece). She said that the issue of an EPC became a routine work and it is usually done in the direction to achieve the necessary energy class for the building.

The part of the recommendations for the energy upgrade in the EPC, is not elaborated essentially but rather typically, it does not consist an important part of the EPC.

She added that many new engineers are asking for information and training. From her view, training should be provided and not just once but regularly.

Finally, she said that trainers should be highly qualified to provide not just theoretical knowledge but also on-site training.

Mr. K. L. (Technical Chamber of Greece) stated that the quality of EPCs is not good. It was suggested that building owners from their side have to understand the value of an EPC and press for their good quality. The Chamber and other institutions could support awareness campaigns. He believes that there is need for exams every 3 years but not a need for specific obligatory training. In any case, the decision lays under political decisions.

Mrs. M.A having heard the Crosscert results, about existing differences in training, legislation etc. between European countries, wondered how homogeneity in EPCs could be achieved.

Mrs. M.P mentioned regarding the sustainability that the training should follow a legislative framework. Besides, she proposed that there could be a team of energy inspectors instead of one common profile, each one specialized to a sector, who could complement each other, especially when it comes to block of buildings.

Closing, G. Koras, E. Taxeri and K. Papadopoulou thanked participants and promised to keep them updated with project outcomes.

Focus Group Event: Visualising building energy performance: Face-to-face EU-level event with invited stakeholders

19 October 2023, 17:00 – 19:00 Camera di Commercio Modena, in Modena, Italy

The event, organized by the Climate Alliance in the framework of the HORIZON 2020 project [crossCert](#) in collaboration with the [Buildings Working Group](#) of Climate Alliance Municipalities, took place at the [Climate Alliance & Energy Cities International Conference 2023](#), on the **19th of October at 17:00 – 19:00 in English at the Camera di Commercio Modena**, in Modena, Italy. The event was free of charge, registration required. Catering was provided in the framework of the conference. A limited number of invited participants had the chance to have their travel costs to Modena reimbursed (requests were processed on a first come, first served basis).

This focus group session was organised by Climate Alliance to investigate the influence of public debates and media coverage on societal perceptions of building energy performance and certification schemes with relevant stakeholders. The focus group session aimed to explore:

- What influence, if any, do public debates and their media coverage have on the society's perception of the energy performance of buildings and its certification schemes?
- How does the media opinion shape our perception of EPC?
- How do these perceptions shape media opinion?
- How, if at all, do media influence the society's perceptions, opinions on and acceptance of regulatory measures, specifically those related to energy efficiency measures in buildings and certification?

For this purpose, various experts working closely or indirectly with EPC in different European countries were identified as relevant and were invited to share their experiences with EPC. The most important selection criterion was good geographical distribution as well as the diversity of the profiles of the experts in contact with the EPCs (engineer, consultant, journalist, department head, academic, etc.). The discussion dealt with the perception and media representation of EPCs. The diversity of perspectives due to geographical distribution, the political situation of a country or the level of expertise enriches the exchange and presents a range of perspectives that is particularly interesting for our research.

Experts from Croatia, France, Hungary, Austria, Germany, Greece, Spain, Italy and Slovenia were taking part in the focus group discussion:

Administration

Experts representing different levels of government organisation for example Administration employees of a city, region or a metropolis (Climate Protection Manager/ Head of Department/...)

Economy

A Regional Development Agency

Scientific Community

Scientist and consultant with a focus on Energy Efficiency and EPC (for ex. On behalf of the Next-Gen EPC Project Cluster)

Media

a journalist specialising in climate protection topics and, in particular, energy saving and efficiency in buildings

First, after a round of introductions, an introduction was given by Climate Alliance to explain in which context the focus group discussion took place. By context, we mean the state of progress of negotiations concerning the EPBD at the European level, but also the context of the crossCert project in which this discussion is taking place.

Afterwards, the participants were interviewed on the following questions:

- 1) Where do you recognise the presence of Energy Performance Certificates in your daily practice?
How are the expected changes in the EU regulations related to buildings discussed publicly in your country? Are the EPCs mentioned in this public discussion? If yes, Positively, negatively, or neutrally?
- 2) Do Energy Performance Certificates play a role in your national and local debates on increasing energy efficiency of buildings?

- 3) Are there / Were there any kind of communication campaigns in your country related to Energy Performance Certificates of buildings? (similar to the EE labels of appliances?)
- 4) Are you aware of any misinformation strategy used in the media related to the energy performance of buildings?
If yes, how do you think this influences public opinion?
If yes, how do you think this influences policy decision-making?
- 5) How do you think is best to support the implementation of a law in terms of efficiency and social acceptance? Which strategies should policymakers have?

Results of the focus group discussion

The presence of Energy Performance Certificates in your daily practice/daily life

Although the EPCs are mandatory in European countries for residential and non-residential buildings for sale or lease and buildings open to the public, practice shows that there is a wide disparity in the application of this legislation from one country to another. All the participants reported that EPCs were present in their country, at least in the case of Greece and Spain. In general, EPCs are almost always displayed at the entrance in buildings open to the public, in advertisements of real-estate agencies for renting or selling dwellings, and on the websites of institutional bodies like energy agencies.

EPCs are rarely presented when a building is offered for sale or rent from one private person to another. **Very few people seem to be aware of their rights or obligations concerning EPCs.**

Public discussion of the EU regulations related to buildings

We have 2 very different cases, depending on the country. The first is the total absence of any discussion of the EPBD and the EPCs in the media. In this case, when there are discussions, they take place between experts within the ministries, the energy agencies or between experts working with the EPCs but who are not present in the media. Of course, the rise in the price of fossil fuels to power heating systems has led to newspaper articles and discussions among people who were afraid of the explosion in costs, but these articles or discussions have not led to discussions about the solutions to be implemented.

these articles or discussions have not led to discussions about the solutions to be implemented.

In the second situation, as was the case in Greece, Italy and Germany, the debate on the revision of the EPBD and/or its adaptation (transcription) into national law was appropriated by conservative and/or populist politicians even before a debate could take place. They spread messages in the media such as "Housing Armageddon", „Europe is asking something very challenging“, „we will lose money“, and „the properties will lose value“, It was presented in a very bad way, the way to say Europe is bad and is asking something which is not feasible, bringing also something not very right correct information about what was the changes about. No debate could take place involving experts, lobbyists, ... and people to explain what about are the planned modifications and why they are useful, necessary and what are the benefits. The tone for the

exchanges was given by communicating messages feeding the fears and concerns of property owners.

Role of EPC in public debate: Communication campaigns in your country related to Energy Performance Certificates of buildings

Basically, it can be said that in almost all countries, there is a certain amount of communication about EPCs, either by private companies wishing to sell their products or through subsidy programs, etc. For example, in countries where EPCs have little or no presence, there is often some form of communication about them, which can be interpreted as the presence of the EPC in the country. The communication campaigns mentioned by participants are briefly presented below.

Private companies sometimes run their own campaigns to promote EPCs. It's a kind of marketing strategy (example/media/...) In France, there was a campaign to promote energy certificates about two years ago, after a thorough reworking of the EPCs in terms of method, design and the information contained in the document (see example).

Exiconomo 2021/2022/2023(Greece) It is an ongoing campaign not exactly on EPC but it is a funding program for renovation related to EPC because the prerequisite is to renovate at least by two energy classes, There are two different kind of campaigns: one for residential building and the other for non-residentials. It is something which is fairly well known, but it's much smaller than the campaign implies. There is a very large number of applications every year, The communication campaign is attached to the brand. Each time the programme starts they provide a lot of useful explanations of what has to happen and mentioned EPC.

In Germany, Information about EPC are communicated through the German Energy Agency and the German consumer organization „die Verbraucherzentrale“ like What is EPC? How is it to read? And what it means?

Awareness of any misinformation strategy used in the media related to energy performance of buildings and related influence of public opinion and /or influence of policy decision-making

On this question, it can perhaps be said that the term „strategy“is considered too strong by the participants. The persons who answered this question were mainly from Germany. They were unanimous about the circulation of a huge amount of false information related to the energy performance of buildings during 2023 in Germany. One newspaper called “Bild Zeitung” is mentioned several times concerning the dissemination of false information about the recast of the German Building Energy Act. After that, the debate swept over to social media where it even get bigger and more false information were circulated. This leads to a lot of fears and insecurity among the German population. People became frightened that they would lose their homes. Fact-checking was started by organisations.

The planned policy changes concerning the German Building Energy Act commonly called „heating law“ **were framed in some media as rather just prohibiting people from taking their own decisions about their homes and houses**, which influenced public opinion in a way that the benefits that this law also has in terms of climate change. A question was raised by a municipality concerning the influence of municipalities concerning policy-making But finally concluded that public authorities could be considered as a decision capacity for the politicians ruling the municipality which is not true for the other employees of administrative departments.

Another way of providing false information is the commercialization of the energy performance of buildings by promoting new more efficient housing appliances or a new air conditioner. The high performance of single renovation products is also highlighted by companies like high-performance windows or insulation because of industrial interests. It raises the awareness of what is the energy performance of buildings but it's a very fragmented strategy.

Supporting the implementation of a law in terms of efficiency and social acceptance – Potential strategies for policymakers

„People's acceptance is a precondition for the implementation of a law. Concerning the social acceptance of a law, it's important to consider the wider public debate on the issue of the law and how the planned law will affect people in their everyday lives and how can we translate the planned policy changes to the people for example: what kind of translation is needed, what kind of knowledge needs to be transferred and how does this law have to be framed to be accepted by the people.“

The strategy proposed here is based on the observation made during the summer of 2023 in Germany, while the "debate" on the heating law was in full swing. The municipality which attests to the facts was running an energy consultation campaign during the same time (Energy consultants were going to people's homes and consulting them on the energy efficiency of their dwellings). Property owners were very concerned about this law and used the opportunity to be in direct contact with specialists to ask questions about the issues that worried them. They asked many questions about the planned „heating law“. The feedback of the energy advisors was very positive and they were able to calm down people's concerns and explain the planned changes to people.

Communication (campaigns) and policymakers implementation plans

Participant's main advice: give the floor to people who have credibility at the local level

- formulate messages in the following way:
 - be simple,
 - be inclusive with your language
 - repeat yourself a lot
 - be aware of the time frame, the implication of decisions, the context
 - explain why the decision is necessary
 - Learn from experience
 - Consider that there are political parties that say „climate change doesn't exist“
 - To address your message, answer first: Who are the house owners? How old are they? What media do they consume? (Information available on the internet is not enough) : communicate the advantages and social benefits of supporting building renovation, Speak about the financial aspects, Teaching/pedagogy, Use local media / Which media works well on a local level?
 - Consider also the district level, since in some regions this is where the information and advice structures are located
 - Be aware of the fact that your message could be abused by other parties who will not support your ideas
 - Engage energy advisors (There is a great lack of energy advisers)
 - Transfer of information from the national level to the local level is needed using a good information channel
 - People passing on information at a local level, should just be able to adapt the national support to their local context.

„Before the law will be voted, a public debate should take place on the best way to implement it. Then it must be some campaigns, elaborated **before** the law with enough time and resources.“

Conclusion

The presence of Energy Performance Certificates in the public space differs from one country to another in Europe. In general, Energy Performance Certificates and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive are rarely discussed in the media. When they are, the discussion often starts with a leakage from a politician, a newspaper or someone who wants to influence the angle of discussion in the media in a negative way. The participants put forward some very constructive solutions, based on their experience in the field, to introduce new laws and act strategically to ensure that media debates are based on facts and not emotions. They concluded by suggesting that any new law must be accompanied by a communication strategy.

Denmark: 2nd National Engagement Event (Info and Discussion Stand at two days national Conference)

[Webinar: Making Energy Performance Visible](#) *Digital Workshop*

September 28, 2022

The Main Takeaways: Various tools, methods, standards and certificates exist to make energy performance visible, in new builds and retrofits. Navigating the maze of what is mandatory and optional as well as what makes the most sense locally can be difficult – especially given differing national and even regional requirements. The streamlining of energy performance certificates and the methodology behind them would be a step in the right direction, but how do such mandatory certificates stack up against more ambitious performance standards?

This online Working Group on buildings with and for municipalities was organised in collaboration with the outPHIT project during Climate Alliance International Conference. At this meeting, participants discussed EPCs as policy tools; how they can be used, how they should be used and how other standards such as the Passive House standards relate to them.

Presentations

ENERGY PERFORMANCE CERTIFICATES AS POLICY TOOLS FOR MUNICIPALITIES

Domen Bančič, Institute for Innovation and Development, University of Ljubljana

An overview of how complex the landscape is nationally and how energy performance certificates are being exploited to design renovation and sustainable building policies at the municipal level, asking the question of how to develop them in the future. Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are social objects, not just technical tools. Thus it is important to focus on people-centred development of EPCs and understand how EPCs influence the construction market and how they can help their users to understand the characteristics of the building they refer to. In order to reach climate neutrality, municipalities should motivate people to renovate their buildings and thus achieve higher energy efficiency of the building stock. Making EPCs more user-friendly and easily understandable supports the renovation and/or building process between experts and non-experts. A key question for the future use of EPCs is: how can EPCs be used to build trust in renovations and shift priorities. The crossCert project set out to explore this key question. Are there any differences in how different countries see and use EPCs?

Yes, especially as they have different histories in terms of their implementation in each country and even on the regional level. Northern countries typically already had a system in place, whereas EPCs were

the first such system for many countries in the South. In Germany, for example, higher energy performance comes with higher rental or selling prices.

GOING ABOVE AND BEYOND IN BUILDING ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND RENEWABLES

Jan Steiger, Passive House Institute

EPC's form the basis in many respects, but some standards that go above and beyond the basics. Jan Steiger looked into how they add up a focus on the Passive House standard for new builds as well as EnerPHit for renovations – perhaps the most ambitious international performance-based building standards. He gave an overview of the standards and what it takes to reach them – high levels of insulation and airtightness, triple-paned windows (in most climates), ventilation with heat recovery and thermal bridge free (or reduced) planning. These standards form the basis of the outPHit project and its case studies. The idea – energy efficiency first and foremost, combined with renewables whenever possible.

Is there an overview of how much (roughly, on average) extra a Passive House building costs compared to a German, low-energy kfw55 house? How long is the payback period on a Passive House?

There is a study done about 10 yrs ago showing that the cheapest renovation was the highest standard. It really depends on the building design though. Typically, you can expect ca. 5 % additional costs for a Passive House, but it depends on the design. If it pays off financially depends how long you live in the building. The economic viability over 20-30 , it also depends on funding/subsidies.

During the discussion it was highlighted that in Germany, only politicians can push the importance of such measuring instruments. Thoughts on how we can promote more rigorous standards were exchanged: we need to focus on the particular groups that make up the EPC system and think about if we have these tools. Difficulties include the differences across EU countries, which crossCert is trying to overcome. We don't need a perfect EPC, the idea is to have it like an identity card to understand how my building performs and to be an indicator of the quality of the property. The key to make EPCs better used is communication: it can be done by the municipalities, real estate agents, architects – people who understand what the EPC expresses and who are communicators. As long as we don't have this communication working, it will just be a piece of paper. Perhaps we need to also focus on the players surrounding/using the EPC system.

It was also highlighted that if an EPC doesn't tell me what I am getting, then it is not a good communication tool. An EPC or any communication tool can only be as good as the data it is based on.

To further deepen this it was highlighted that people are an important element of the EPC system. They can explain what is in the EPCs and what it is good for. The EPC assessors / energy advisors who understand the technical side as well. It was added that both EPCs and certificates of other types are necessary. It is confusing in Germany that funding standards have no clear indication of the energy demand of the concrete building but it is a referential building. It is not clear how that is related to the real performance. If I look at an EPC I want to know what this building will cost me if I look at my energy bills.

crossCert Open events and digital workshops/webinars M18-36

Previously organised events in Month 1-18 can be found in the D7.2 Interim Communication and Dissemination Report.

6th Final Webinar: Energy Performance Assessment and Certification of Buildings: The future of EPCs

21 November 2024 | 10:00-11:03 CET | online

The final crossCert Webinar presenting 3 years of research results

Presentation of results - PDF Download of Webinar Slideshow

[crossCert_final_webinar_presentation.pdf](#)

Main Project Results in a Nutshell - PDF Download

[crossCert_Results_Final.pdf](#)

Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) are a central part of energy efficiency legislation in buildings throughout Europe. Next-generation EPCs have a great potential to be more useful. The detailed analysis of existing EPCs in crossCert was accompanied by detailed research how EPCs could be added to existing national databases and renovation one-stop shops, how they could make the most of both existing and future tools like energy audits, building logbooks and building renovation passports, and how they could help end-users and potential investors to understand the full potential and multidimensionality of building renovations.

This webinar targeted EPC assessors, policymakers for building policies related to EPCs, practitioners and experts involved in applied research, building managers and property owners. The recording is available on [Youtube](#).

Agenda

10.05 CET Introduction and testing results of EU certification procedures on 140 buildings

Prof. Noberto Fueyo Díaz, University of Zaragoza, Spain

10.15 CET Evaluating technical differences in EPCs across Europe, and why that matters

Prof. David Jenkins, Urban Energy Research Group, Institute of Sustainable Built Environment, Heriot-Watt University, UK

10.25 CET The value of EPC's: Success stories

Milka Hrbud, dipl. ing. el., REGEA North-West Croatia Regional Energy and Climate Agency, Croatia

10.35 CET Making EPCs more people-centred: optimizing EPCs from the user perspective

Domen Bančič, Senior Research Associate, IRI-UL Institute for Innovation and development, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

10.45 CET Harmonising EPCs in Europe

Elena Taxeri, Energy Planning Supporting Systems, Centre for Renewable Energy Sources & Energy Saving (CRES), Greece

[Webinar: New perspectives for impactful communication campaigns on energy-efficient renovations](#)

28 August 2024 | 11:00-12:00 CET | online

This webinar was organised as a satellite online offer related to the Climate Alliance Annual Conference 2024 and was aimed at giving an insight into the results of the research conducted related to the Marketing and communication of EPCs.

Current communication campaigns focus mostly on financial aspects, considering that property owners make rational decisions motivated by financial factors and energy savings (EPCs are rarely mentioned in promotion and marketing campaigns). According to the literature, these aspects are not the primary

motivators for the energy renovation of buildings. To be efficient, communication campaigns should focus on the homeowner's life cycle and consider the trigger points for renovation. Communication campaigns should deliver inspiring messages to homeowners and provide them with easy-to-understand, highly visual information. In addition, easy access to reliable information through the internet, telephone, flyers, newspaper articles, etc. should be provided by the government, scientific organisations or consumer organisations for ex. free or low-cost energy renovation advice should also be part of their long-term renovation strategy.

Various ways and formats for homeowners, their friends, relatives, neighbours, and families to interact with professionals should be proposed. Informal exchanges among these groups are where most information about energy-efficient renovations is shared. Positive or negative experiences, reliable technical information, and misinformation spread within these exchanges can significantly impact how energy-efficient renovations are perceived and can influence whether a renovation project moves forward or is abandoned.

Anne Turfin (Building engineer, Climate Alliance) offered an insight in how campaigns should resonate with property owners through storytelling and highlight benefits beyond technical details, like indoor comfort. In her recent study, Anne analysed trust and reliable information and how these are crucial in communicating using EPCs to boost energy efficient renovations. Anne also examines media influence on public opinion using the example of the German Building Energy Code debate, recommending strategies to mitigate financial impacts and address public fears.

Related Resources:

[Recording of the webinar](#)

Presentation: Impactful campaigns on energy-efficient renovations - Presentation by Anne Turfin

[CAIC2024_Communication_campaigns.pdf](#) 3 MB

Report on promotion and marketing of EPC (Energy Performance Certificate) products and services

[crossCert_D5.4_Report_on_promotion_and_marketing_of_EPCs.pdf](#) 9 MB

Policy Conference: Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates Conference – EPBD Recast Edition

23 May 2024, 9:00 – 17:30 CEST | Mundo Madou, Brussels

The 2024 Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) Conference was organised in the greater context of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) Recast to bring forward valuable insights and applicable outcomes. Moving towards the completion of the Horizon 2020 funded projects crossCert, EPC RECAST, EUB SuperHub and iBRoad2EPC, the joint conference was held on 23 May 2024, physically at Mundo Madou, Brussels. The four projects, each unique with its own perspective on the issue of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), presented their insights and outcomes and discuss with their peers during four sessions by setting the scene, providing an overview of policy-related outcomes and applicable solutions, deep diving into the Key Exploitable Results of the projects and providing third party feedback and views. Participation in the event was free of charge, but prior registration was required. The event was streamed online, the recording of the stream [is available here](#).

The conference was organised in four parts, starting with the policy context, moving onto overall project outcomes, then focusing on specific Key Exploitable Results, and concluding with extensive discussions with national energy agencies and market representatives. The event was live-streamed and recorded and is now available to be watched on demand.

Part 1 – Policy context (Moderated by Andrei Vladimir Litiu, [EPB Center](#))

- **Pau Garcia Audi, European Commission, DG ENER/B.3:** focused on the recast Energy Performance of Buildings Directive and broader regulatory framework.
- **Sylvain Robert, Project Manager at CINEA,** focused on relevant Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and LIFE calls for proposals funding and the respective projects.
- **Hélène Sibileau, Buildings Performance Institute Europe – BPIE,** focused on important links and potential gaps or missing elements between Energy Performance Certificates and Renovation Passports.

A quick introduction to each of the four organising projects, including their complementary perspectives, was presented by the coordinators:

- On behalf of [crossCert](#), by **Norberto Fueyo, University of Zaragoza**
- On behalf of [EPC RECAST](#), by **Olivier Greslou, CSTB**
- On behalf of [EUB SuperHub](#), by **Peter Gyuris, Geonardo**
- On behalf of [iBRoad2EPC](#), by **Alexander Deliyannis, Sympraxis**

Part 2 – Overview of insights and outcomes (Moderated by Alice Corovessi, [INZEB](#)) provided a bird's eye view of the four project's perspectives and results.

The Horizon 2020 project **crossCert** was presented by **Norberto Fueyo, University of Zaragoza**. The project contributes to the next generation of EPCs by performing a detailed, bottom-up analysis of EPC methodologies in ten participating EU countries. The key elements of this approach are:

- Cross-testing, mainly by energy agencies or similar entities, of current EPCs and new EPC initiatives, on around 140 buildings in ten European countries;
- Analysing and comparing the results from the different national approaches;
- Identifying, in the process, good practices that include potential improvements on accuracy, usability and harmonisation;
- Outreach, which includes the creation of a public repository of building data, and the engagement of networks and alliances of third-party actors for analysis.

The Horizon 2020 project **EPC RECAST**, presented by **Olivier Greslou, CSTB**, sets a structured process and toolbox supporting the implementation and validation of a new generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification for residential buildings, for which retrofit is a challenging and pressing issue. By improving the usability, reliability and comparability of EPCs, and linking them to renovation roadmaps and digital logbooks, EPC RECAST contributes to improved working practices of EPC assessors and user awareness of building efficiency. The Horizon 2020 project **EUB SuperHub** consortium carried out an extensive exercise, involving building experts and policy experts, to conclude a set of 21 Key Performance Indicators for building assessments that go beyond building energy performance and set a holistic view on buildings according to the EPBD. The indicators are tested on more than 100 buildings across various European climates. This assessment process is supported by the Digital Building Logbook developed by the project. The social acceptance studies of the project characterised the stakeholders' motivation towards EPCs and analysed public engagement and education programmes to develop guidelines. The presentation was given by **Andrea Moro, iISBE Italy**. The Horizon 2020 project **iBRoad2EPC** was presented by **Marianna Papaglastra, Sympraxis**. iBRoad2EPC developed and tested a flexible and affordable model building Renovation Passport that integrates with the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC), to guide and motivate building owners to undertake staged deep renovations. iBRoad2EPC adds an appropriate individual building renovation plan as well as new indicators –for Indoor Environmental Quality, Smart Readiness, Measured Energy Performance and others– into the established national EPC schemes in a modular and expandable fashion. An integral part of the long-term renovation plan provided by iBRoad2EPC are future legal regulations and obligations resulting from European or national legislation, e.g., phase-out of fossil fuel fired boilers, national implementation of minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) as foreseen in the 2024 recast EPBD, etc. Following presentations of the individual projects, a summary overview mapping the four projects' focus on common and complementary aspects was presented by **Alexander Deliyannis, Sympraxis**.

In Part 3, moderated by Gunnar Grün, [Fraunhofer IBP](#), each project dived deeper into its Key Exploitable Results

The key outputs from **crossCert** as presented by **Professor David Jenkins**, [Heriot-Watt University](#):

- A comparative analysis of the EPC methodologies in participating countries.
- A quantitative estimation of the so-called performance gap in participating buildings, and an analysis of its possible sources, together with a discussion of the relevance of the performance gap as a metric for EPC effectiveness.
- An analysis of the new scales and Key Performance Indicators either as proposed in EU R&D projects or being discussed in participating countries.
- Proposals for increasing the value of EPCs through their use in databases, and their linkage with energy audits, Digital Building Logbooks, and building Renovation Passports.
- An analysis of current EPC designs and their user experiences, and guidelines and recommendations for development of people-centred EPC products and services.
- Recommendations for EPC harmonisation, and for a harmonised EPC verification framework for quality checking EPC outputs.
- An openly-accessible database of building data for selected buildings in the EU and UK countries participating in crossCert, the European OpenAIRE programme.
- The Knowledge Exchange Centre, a web-based repository of information on next generation Energy Performance Certificates for buildings in the European Union.
- A wide-ranging engagement of stakeholders through multiple channels (social media, website, newsletters, national stakeholder events, and international focus groups, networking events and policies conferences).

The key outputs from **EPC RECAST** as presented by **Sarah Noyé**, [Tecnalia](#):

- An integrated methodology and workflow to improve daily working practices of EPC assessors with a set of digital tools and protocols, from the on-site visit to the issuing of the EPC and renovation recommendations.
- A common data model of the building for EPCs implemented in XML format as the core/foundation of EPC RECAST's digital toolbox and integrated workflow.
- Conversion algorithms and some 'standard values' to connect the data model with dynamic energy simulation engines, ensuring compliance with ISO/CEN standards developed under the European Commission mandate to CEN M/480.
- Input/output data interfaces in the EPC RECAST toolbox and strategies to connect the data model and digital tools, following the principles of a common data environment. Long-term monitoring implemented in 50% of the pilot dwellings and direct feedback from EPC assessors.
- Policy and market uptake recommendations related to the transposition of the recast EPBD.

EUB SuperHub's key outputs as presented by **Elena Mocchio** and **Fabio Rossi**, [UNI](#) include:

- Selected KPIs, plus qualification needs of experts to use building KPIs according to EU norms (EN ISO), leading to development of the EUB SuperHub CEN Workshop Agreement to assess and certify buildings by skilled professionals (exploiting the TRAIN4SUSTAIN project CWA 17939-2022).
- KPIs meeting with the EPBD 2024 provisions for applications that also go beyond building energy performance, including life-cycle approach (GWP), quality of life for occupants (IAQ), climate and future proof indicators (SRI, resilience).
- Storage and management of geo-referenced EPCs on an online platform, further supplying building information and supported by a Digital Building Logbook, boosted with the project specific KPIs and the EUB Passport, as annex in a One-Stop Shop (building certification, marketplace, training).
- A set of 21 KPIs needing upskilled assessors, trained to use the necessary –online– tools as well.
- Training material, assessment and testing results on 100+ case study buildings across seven EU Member States on different European climates, also used to upgrade the method.
- Social acceptance studies constituting
 1. Mapping of stakeholders and understanding of the needs of market actors with respect to EPC certificates and assessment schemes
 2. Principles, guidelines for public engagement and education.

For **iBRoad2EPC**, the key outputs were presented by **Peter Mellwig**, [ifeu](#):

- iBRoad2EPC's adaptable database of country specific renovation advice, including climatic regions, energy classes, milestones, MEPS, obligations, targets, technical specifications, costs, etc.
- iBRoad2EPC Assistant: the software used by energy assessors to produce the Renovation Passport, consisting of a basic standardised country-specific module, expandable upon demand with various additional modules, including the currently developed Indoor Environment Quality module, Measured Energy Performance Module, Smart Readiness Indicator module, Energy Demand module, and Cost-Investment module.
- iBRoad2EPC: the Renovation Passport itself, as an online document and printable page, complementing the EPC with a step-by-step renovation plan to fulfil national obligations and own targets, improve conditions for the building user, avoid mis-investments, and including information/advice on indoor quality, smart readiness, cost, etc.

The interactive Part 4 – Third party feedback and views, moderated by Rui Fragoso, [ADENE](#)

This session gathered input from energy agencies and market representatives, organised around two panel discussions:

- Panel "From project results to EPBD implementation: The Energy Agencies perspective" with representatives from the [Austrian Energy Agency \(Nicole Hartl\)](#), the Greek Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving – [CREG \(Andreas Androutsopoulos\)](#), the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development – [ENEA \(Fabio Zanghirella\)](#) and The Polish National Energy Conservation Agency – [KAPE \(Karolina Junak\)](#)
- Panel "A market look at the recast EPBD implementation: how can the four projects' outcomes help?" with representatives from EuroACE – [Efficient Buildings Europe \(Rémi Collombet\)](#),

European Builders Confederation – [EBC](#) (**Spyros Mathioudakis**) and the European Federation of Intelligent Energy Efficiency Services – [EFIEES](#) (**Valérie Plainemaison**)

- Verbal statement by the European Public Real Estate Association – [EPRA](#) (**Jean-Marie Simon**)

The event concluded with closing remarks from **Ulriche Nuscheler**, Project Manager at **CINEA**. The full conference recording is available to view on demand via YouTube [here](#).

[crossCert at the World Sustainable Energy Days Conference](#)

March 5, 2024 | Wels, Austria

Our colleague, Antonio Gómez (University of Zaragoza) presented the project's objectives, methodology, and the results we have achieved from the cross-testing activities at the Poster session of the Conference. The results focused on the experiment on building energy performance certificates (EPCs). The process of applying one country's certification methodology to buildings from another country has been challenging due to differences in climate data, language and terms, and treatment of certain building elements and features such as thermal bridges or user behaviour in the energy rating calculation.

The comparison of the results obtained with the EPC methodologies of the testing countries and hosting countries for the same building has shown a consistency of the EPC results across Europe that is better than the initial expectations. In the journey to carry out the cross testing, many difficulties have had to be overcome, and hypotheses and estimates had to be made to apply certifications from hosting countries to testing buildings. For these reasons, conflicting results were expected from EPC methodologies from different countries.

The consistency of EPC results across Europe is relevant when defining common building renovation policies in the EU based on the energy classes of the building stock. The labels standardize the numerical values obtained, harmonizing the results among countries.

The Poster can [be downloaded here](#).

[Webinar: Funding Options for Energy-Efficient Building Renovations Across Europe](#)

February 27, 2024 | online

Energy renovation can be very expensive. Incentives and Funding to renovate underperforming buildings are crucial for achieving a decarbonized building stock in all EU countries. These incentives can take the form of obligations, such as phasing out fossil-fueled boilers, or financial support in the form of funding programs, tax reductions, subsidies for individual renovation roadmaps, or mandatory and subsidized energy efficiency advice. These funding schemes can influence investment decisions and motivate people to invest in the energy efficiency of their buildings. The revision of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive emphasizes the importance of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) as tools not only to express the measured energy efficiency grade of a building but also as a marketing tool for citizens to demonstrate the value of their properties. Our webinar focused on the financial perspectives and the role of EPCs in the renovation process.

Speakers: **Rui Fragoso**, Head of Buildings and Efficiency of Resources at ADENE, Portugal's National Energy Agency, **Jana Lange**, Expert for Energy Efficiency and Heating in Buildings at the Franco-German Office for Energy Transition (OFATE), **Nicole Hartl**, Senior Expert at the Centre for Climate Neutral Buildings & Neighbourhoods at the Austrian Energy Agency

This webinar delved into funding schemes for energy-efficient building renovations and the significance of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) in accessing these subsidies. Rui Fragoso began with a presentation underscoring the pivotal role of EPCs in guiding policy-making and facilitating renovation efforts. He emphasized their importance in Portugal's support programs and the forthcoming EPBD changes. The panel discussion featured Rui Fragoso, Jana Lange, and Nicole Hartl, providing insights into financing programs across four European countries. They highlighted the integration of funding programs with regulatory frameworks, information dissemination, and training initiatives. In closing, panelists offered recommendations for countries without funding programs, emphasizing simplicity, alignment with building needs, long-term planning, and streamlined processes.

This online event started with a presentation by Rui Fragoso, in which he addressed the crucial role of energy performance certificates in supporting policy-making, promoting renovation efforts and supporting stakeholders. "Gaining insight into the building stock has been key to creating tools to facilitate its improvement," said Rui Fragoso, who has been following and influencing the development of EPCs at both national and European levels for many years.

He outlined the important role played by EPCs in Portugal in support programmes, as well as in the CASA+ one-stop-shop, before concluding with some news on EPCs in the forthcoming EPBD. He also highlighted the important role of financial institutions in providing the capital needed to successfully meet the challenge of energy efficient building renovation.

Following the presentation, during the panel discussion, Mr Fragoso discussed with Jana Lange, and Nicole Hartl the current national funding landscape drivers of energy efficient renovations and the role of EPCs. This discussion gave us a good overview of the specificities of financing programmes for energy renovation in these 4 European countries.

The three speakers agreed that funding programmes do not exist in isolation, but are intertwined with other instruments such as regulatory frameworks, information centres, specialised training and effective communication strategies. Funding programmes are mostly similar across Europe. They focus mainly on insulation, replacement of windows and doors, and optimisation of heating systems, as in France and Germany. "France prioritises deep renovation programmes and gives considerable importance to social aspects in the support programmes. In Germany, on the other hand, social aspects have only recently been taken into account in the design of the new support programme for heating systems, e.g. by granting an additional bonus for low-income households," says Jana Lange.

Another special feature in Germany is the possibility of receiving funding for the cost of materials if homeowners carry out the energy renovation work themselves. In France, do-it-yourself energy renovation projects are supported by several agencies. Energy advisors work closely with homeowners to provide helpful advice. This can be a very effective solution, especially in that part of the renovation market where there is a shortage of skilled craft.

Nicole Hartl highlighted the need for better communication between energy advisors, architects and building owners regarding thermal refurbishment. This includes discussing the benefits of retrofitting, the work involved and the future benefits. She emphasised the absolute need for long-term funding programmes to enable work to be planned. One-year funding programmes are too short for businesses or apartment blocks. Planning energy renovation work takes time, especially for multi-family houses, but also financial guarantees, which are not guaranteed when subsidy programmes change regularly. Mr Fragoso made the same observation for Portugal: "Subsidy programmes have a lot of stop-and-go, and this makes work planning very difficult, even for professionals".

In the discussions, the role of EPCs in the funding system were also explored. EPCs are an integral part of the Portuguese funding system. The challenge in Portugal, which revised the EPCs a few years ago (to make them more attractive, more consumer-oriented and less technical), is to get people to read them, Rui Fragoso mentioned. Most EPC owners do not read them. In Austria, an EPC or Energy Performance Certificate is required to obtain funding, making it a fundamental tool in a building renovation journey. Ms Hartl emphasised that even if an EPC is not mandatory to receive funding, the role of EPC issuers (and estate agents) is key to the EPC as they are often in direct contact with property owners. They would be in a position to explain the EPC and possible renovation measures.

In the same time, in France, EPCs played a secondary role, except for deep renovation, Ms Lange added. In the meantime, Germany has already introduced renovation roadmaps, which allow people to get a 5% bonus when they apply for a subsidy for carrying out the recommended renovation measures. Portugal and Austria noted that the nature of the funding applications submitted in most cases consist of individual renovation measures or changes to the heating system, thus deep renovation plays only a secondary role.

Funding programmes for renovation measures for inefficient housing is not necessarily available in every EU country. Participants and the webinar experts key advice for policy-makers for these countries, based on their insights and experiences are to:

- **Keep it as simple as possible.**
- **Give assessment of the current building needs high priority and design the funding schemes according to these building needs.**
- **Plan a long-term funding scheme and design quick and easy administrative processes.**

Webinar: Upgrading EPCs for new challenges - Do all EU countries have to prepare for the same costs of the EPBD?

July 13, 2023 | online

A number of media voices have been suggesting that reaching a better energy classification for buildings in some countries implies higher investment than in others. They portray this as unfair among countries, and this notion seems to be gaining momentum.

How do European-wide ambitions and targets “land” differently across different countries in their renovation efforts? Is it difficult to harmonise new approaches in building energy efficiency when the existing approaches are themselves not harmonised? These were some of the questions we tackled at the 1 hour Webinar with building experts, energy agencies, and more. The discussion was complemented with the most recent findings and insights gained from cross-testing done by crossCert partners using different EU member states methodologies.

A recent article in a German news outlet presented a table comparing the different energy classes of buildings for a number of EU countries, assigning different kwh/m/a values to them. Those values were cited as research and from the EU EPS database. The article suggested that for the same class, a country like Germany or Austria would need to reach a far lower kwh/m/a consumption in their buildings than eg. the Netherlands or Bulgaria. Such media narrative feeds a public opinion that in some EU countries building owners would need to pay a much higher price for the renovation of their buildings, if strict mandatory energy class targets would be set on EU level. In order to examine the numbers and narrative given in the article, the CrossCert team analysed the data given and compared it to the results of the crossCert cross-testing which takes place among different EU countries. In the course of this process, the same buildings are tested along the national methodologies of one country and the results are compared to the results of other countries' EPC methodology, resulting in some compatibility measurements.

The results of the tests demonstrated a relatively high correlation between the methodologies and the energy classes and showed that even if there are differences in calculating the energy classes, the methods might be not that far from each other as the article suggests. Furthermore, crossCert expert Nicole Hartl (Austrian Energy Agency) explained in detail why the numbers in the article are so different from each other. She elaborated that the attempt to compare these classes purely by numbers, is like “comparing apples and oranges”. The examples to demonstrate the differences included among other:

- Some countries' measurements will include lighting, in others not.
- Countries are located in different climate zones that has an influence on energy efficiency
- Some include or exclude heating as well as warm water production etc...

These factors can greatly influence the energy consumption of a building and are therefore important variables in the calculation of the EPC class. Therefore, a much bigger effort must be made to compare the different calculation models across Europe, if reliable data should be produced.

During the open floor with the audience, crossCert experts discussed with the audience the upcoming EPC standards. Prof. Norberto Fueyo highlighted that the upcoming changes on methods will still not be

enough to help harmonize European EPC's, because the differences, as pointed out by Nicole Hartl, are still not properly addressed in the new EPC system and therefore will still cause discrepancies when comparing EPCs across EU countries. [The recording of the Webinar can be watched online.](#)

Participation and Dissemination Events

The Project partnership presented crossCert results at altogether 57 external conferences and events, reaching over 2100 participant stakeholders. A full list of the events with relevant links to the event materials can be found below.

crossCert at external Events	Date	Location	Contribution of crossCert	Partner Name(s)
elevator pitch of crossCert project in the Next Gen EPCerts H2020 cluster - 2nd Non Disclosure Agreement (NDA) workshop	24.06.2021	online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UNIZAR
Presentation at European Researchers' Evening event	24.09.2021	online	Demonstration / Pitch Event / Exhibition, Trade Show	UNIZAR
Round table on Smart Readiness Indicator at Sustainable Places 2021	29.09.2021	online	Participation at Workshop	HWU
Panellist at the EUSEW2021 Extended Programme "The next generation Energy Performance Certificates: making buildings fit for the energy transition"	14.10.2021	online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UNIZAR
Anthropology of Technology Conference, Aarhus University	04.11.2021	In person	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	IRI UL
Presence in booth at EnLit Europe 2021; logo in banner with sister projects	23.11.2021		Demonstration / Pitch Event / Exhibition, Trade Show	UNIZAR
Presentation at European Researchers' Evening event	29.11.2021	In person - Velingrad, Bulgaria and Online	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	ENEFFECT

ETP and H+C Zero Network Webinar - Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates	17.12.2021	online	Participation at Workshop	HWU
SME upravljanje z energijo	22.02.2022	online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	IRI UL
Third national (Spanish) workshop: Project QualDeEPC	11.05.2022	In person	Participation at Workshop	UNIZAR
Presentation at Energy Performance Certificates and Useful Tools Workshop	17.05.2022	In person - Sofia, Bulgaria and online	Participation at Workshop	ENEFFECT
The role of EPCs	17.05.2022	Sofia, hybrid	Participation at Workshop	ENEFFECT
Final Conference PrioritEE PLUS Project: Presentation of the crossCert project (activities, goals): Cross-assessment of EPC, introduction to the concept early results of the crossCert project - Norberto Fueyo	13.06.2022	In person	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	UNIZAR
Enerselves Final Conference	14.06.2022	Karlskrona, Sweden	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	MIEMA
The next generation of EPCs - Challenges & opportunities	14.06.2022	Vienna	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	AEA
Seminar: Cross-assessment and convergence of energy performance certification and buildings' data digitalisation	15.06.2022	In person	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	EREN
Networking Bodega (morning)	15.06.2022	In person	Participation at Workshop	EREN

Enerselves Stakeholder Group Workshop	30.08.2022	Online	Participation at Workshop	MIEMA
Actions to promote energy efficiency in buildings	14.10.2022	in person	Participation at Workshop	CRES
Scottish Energy Technology Partnership researcher event	01.11.2022	Edinburgh	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	HWU
Easy SRI project kickoff meeting	15.11.2022	Hybrid	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	CRES
InCLIMATE International Conference	15.11.2022	Rome, Italy	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	MIEMA
QualDeEPC - the final conference: How energy performance certificates support the deep renovation	15.11.2022	Hybrid	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	REGEA
"Pathways towards green transition of European urban areas" - City Minded Final Conference	22.11.2022	Pula, Croatia	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	MIEMA
3rd workshop of PANACEA project	02.12.2022	online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	CRES
CIBSE workshop - Updates on latest section 6 building regulations in Scotland	15.12.2022	Online	Participation at Workshop	HWU
Cities Go Climate Neutral - Kick-Off Meeting	15.12.2022	Online	Participation at Workshop	MIEMA
Info sesion of Horizon Europe Cluster 5 in Castilla y León	16.01.2023	Valladolid (in person)	Participation at Workshop	EREN

Towards new-generation EPCs	08.02.2023	Sofia, hybrid	Participation at Workshop	ENEFFECT
Energy Efficient Buildings: Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates	28.09.2022	online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	IRI UL
Target training for energy management in buildings	09.03.2023	Ljubljana, Brinje	Training	IRI UL
Joint final conference of D2EPC, EPANACEA, E-DYCE - Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) - Panel Discussion(2)	24.05.2023	Brussels	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	AEA
Sustainable Financing of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Projects	03.06.2023	Burgas, online	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	ENEFFECT
EPSRC H+C Zero Network Summer School	22.08.2023	Durham, UK	Participation at Workshop	HWU
TIMEPAC 2023 International workshop	21.11.2023	Vienna	Participation at Workshop	EREN
TIMEPAC 2023 International workshop	21.11.2023	Vienna	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	AEA
XVII Annual national conference of the Association of Bulgarian Energy Agencies	28.11.2023	Sofia, hybrid	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	ENEFFECT
Webinar for energy advisors with focus on SRI	10.01.2024	Online	Participation at Workshop	IRI UL
ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF THE BUILDING STOCK: THE CORNERSTONE OF THE SUSTAINABLE ENERGY TRANSITION	30.01.2024	Sofia, hybrid	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	ENEFFECT

CIBSE technical symposium 2024	20.04.2024	Cardiff	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	HWU
The EPBD recast - challenges and oportunities	15.05.2024	Sofia, hybrid	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	ENEFFECT
Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates CONFERENCE - EPBD Recast Edition	23.05.2024	Brussels	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	HWU
ECEEE 2024 summer study	10.06.2024	France	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	HWU
Targeted training for energy management in buildings	17.10.2024	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	IRI UL
Yearly expert seminar of EnSvet advisory network	25.10.2024	Solkan, Slovenia	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	IRI UL
IBPSA Building Simulation Conference 2021	1-3 /09/ 2021	Bruges/online	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	HWU
U-CERT National Event	14.-22.12.2022	Ljubljana	Participation at Workshop	IRI UL
At final lectures of University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, course 6602-M SMART CITIES (Pametna mesta) 2nd year of Mechanical Engineering - Research and Development Programme, MSc;	16.1.2024 and 19.1.2024	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Participation at Workshop	IRI UL

Process Mechanical Engineering (major).				
Berlin Energy Days	22-23/05/2023	Berlin, DE	Demonstration / Pitch Event / Exhibition, Trade Show	CA
THE FUTURE OF FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS FOR SUSTAINABLE ENERGY and XXV Annual EcoEnergy Conference	23-24.04.2024	Troyan, hybrid	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	ENEFFECT
ICARB Conference 2023	25-26/9/2023	Edinburgh	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	HWU
Enerselves Interregional Event and Workshop	27 - 28/04/2022	Victoria, Gozo	Participation at Workshop	MIEMA
Mayors Talk conference	3-4.07.24	Gabrovo, hybrid	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	ENEFFECT
IBPSA Building Simulation Conference 2023	4-6/9/2023	Shanghai/on line	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	HWU
World Sustainable Energy Days	5-8/3/2024	Wels (Austria)	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	UNIZAR
European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy (eceee) Summer Study Presented paper relating to crossCert work on next-generation EPCs	6-11 June 2022	Hybrid	Participation at a Conference - includes presentation at conferences	HWU

Publications in scientific and sectoral journals

Over the course of the project, 8 Scientific papers have been published with the results of the project. Some were also presented at scientific conference and published in the relevant Proceedings of the event. Downloadable public papers are also posted on the project website (<https://www.crosscert.eu/our-solutions/scientific-publications>).

Date	Authors	Title	Journal/Publication
Jun 2022	Jenkins, Semple, McCallum	Identifying the case for Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates	ECEEE Summer Study Proceedings
Sep 2021	Jenkins, Semple, Patidar, McCallum	Alternative modelling approaches to energy performance certificates	Building Simulation 2021
Sep 2023	Jenkins, Semple, Mahsa Sayfekar	Investigating the relationship between energy assessor training and assessment methodology in standardised energy assessments in Europe	Building Simulation 2023
Sep 2023	Sayfekar, Jenkins	Variations of input parameters in EPCs calculation methodologies across European countries	ICARB 2023
Apr 2024	Sayfekar, Jenkins	EPC calculation methodologies across Europe and accommodating new performance indicators	CIBSE Technical Symposium
June 2024	Sayfekar, Jenkins	Energy performance certificates in Europe – their differences and why that matters	ECEEE 2024 SUMMER STUDY
Sep 2024	Sayfekar, Jenkins	Energy performance certificate calculation methodologies across Europe and accommodating new performance indicators	Building Services Engineering Research & Technology

Sep 24	M. Sayfekar, D. Jenkins, A. Gómez, N. Fueyo	A Comparative Study of Energy Performance Certificates across Europe	Buildings
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Dissemination at scientific events included:

- 2021: Presentation at European Researchers' Evening event (ENEFFECT)
- 2021: Anthropology of Technology Conference, Aarhus University (IRI-UL)
- 2022: European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy (eceee) Summer Study | Presented paper relating to work on next-generation EPCs (HWU)
- 2022: Final Conference PrioritEE PLUS Project (UNIZAR)
- 2022: Seminar: Cross-assessment and convergence of energy performance certification and buildings' data digitalisation (EREN)
- 2022: Scottish Energy Technology Partnership researcher event (HWU)
- 2022: Enerselves Final Conference, InCLIMATE International Conference (MIEMA)
- 2022: "Pathways towards green transition of European urban areas" - City Minded Final Conference (MIEMA)
- 2023: IBPSA Building Simulation Conference
- ICARB Conference 2023
- World Sustainable Energy Days 2023 and 2024
- XVII Annual national conference of the Association of Bulgarian Energy Agencies
- ECEEE 2024 summer study
- CIBSE technical symposium 2024

Key Performance Indicators

Dissemination and communication activities combined with stakeholder engagement activities reached over **107823 external stakeholders** and target group representatives, **24503** newsletter (project and partner newsletters) subscribers; crossCert content on social media generated over **76134** reach/impressions. Overall **1592** target group representatives participated in crossCert stakeholder events, and **2130** stakeholders participated at external events where crossCert was presented.

The KPIs were all met and in most cases exceeded many times over. Impressions and traffic on social media as well as on the website always saw a sharp increase around the times of crossCert events like webinars, workshops or participation at shared conferences. In its final year, now equipped with a host of project results, crossCert project partners organized or participated in 8 events, which in turn produced very active online traffic.

KPI Name	KPI Goal	KPI Current Number
Building Owners	200	993
Certification bodies	20	70
Citizens (General Public)	1000	96112
Energy Agencies	70	716
Energy Auditors	500	877
EPC Issuers	500	1186
Financing providers	100	382
Professionals in the construction sector	250	1213
Public authorities	250	2872
Researchers	300	1665
Sectoral associations	50	1737
Altogether		107823

Communication activities		
Project logo / Visual identity	Available on month 02	Done
Newsletter	One every 6 months	6
Website	Available on month 05	Done
LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Researchgate	> 1000 contacts	Impressions*Views 76134
Attendance to conferences, events, workshops	> 15	21
Events organised by crossCert (workshops, webinars, etc.)	> 30	56
Knowledge exchange centre	Operational on month 15	Done
Press publications	> 20	2
Articles published in scientific journals	> 5	8

Dissemination and communication activities in numbers

Category	Number
Organisation of a Conference	1
Organisation of a Workshop	19
Press release	0
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	2
Exhibition	n/a
Training	1
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	
Participation to a Conference	23
Participation to a Workshop	18
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	0
Brokerage Event	0
Pitch Event	3
Trade Fair	0
Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	12
Other	0

Estimated number of persons reached	Number	Type of Target Group
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1665	Researchers
Industry	3276	Energy Auditors, EPC Issuers, Professionals in the construction sector
Civil Society	1737	Sectoral associations
General Public	96112	Citizens
Policy Makers	3658	Public Authorities, Certification bodies, Energy Agencies
Media		
Investors	382	Financing Providers
Customers	993	Building owners
Other		
Altogether	107823	

Conclusions

All and all the results in WP7 are satisfactory, with high outreach registered particularly thanks to the engagement of all partners. Communication materials were created specifically related to stakeholder engagement and the project results were thoroughly discussed with sister projects and through networking. The communication channels were used according to plan and particularly the newsletters and the LinkedIn channel reached key stakeholders. Promotional materials, project website, project newsletter, social media channels and additional communication materials were supporting dissemination in our outreach target groups and project results were disseminated in usually around crossCert events. Participation in relevant academic dissemination actions are undertaken by academic partners and energy agencies.

Annex A: Key Stakeholders engaged via the Next-Gen EPC EU Level event

EU	Municipalities	Climate Alliance Members, Buildings Working Group	Municipalities' Association	https://www.climatealliance.org/municipalities/the-network.html
EU	Energy Agencies	FEDARENE	Energy Agency Association	https://fedarene.org/
EU	Sectoral associations (green building councils, NGOs)	Federation of European Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning Associations (REHVA)	Association of HVAC designers, building services engineers, technicians and experts	https://www.rehva.eu/about-us/who-we-are/about-rehva
EU	EPC users	BEUC - The European Consumer Organisation	Umbrella group of 46 independent consumer organisations from 32 countries	https://www.beuc.eu/about-beuc/who-we-are
EU	Sectoral associations (green building councils, NGOs)	BPIE - Buildings Performance Institute Europe	Europe's leading independent think tank on energy performance of buildings	https://www.bpie.eu/about-us/
EU	Sectoral associations (green building councils, NGOs)	BPIE - Buildings Performance Institute Europe	Europe's leading independent think tank on energy performance of buildings	https://www.bpie.eu/about-us/
EU	EPC users	Housing Europe	European Federation of Public, Cooperative &	https://www.housingeurope.eu/

			Social Housing	
EU	Sectoral associations (green building councils, NGOs)	RAP - The Regulatory Assistance Project	NGO think tank advancing policy innovation and thought leadership within the energy community	https://www.raponline.org/about/
EU	Sectoral associations (green building councils, NGOs)	International Copper Association (ICA)	NGO bringing together the copper industry and its partners	https://copperalliance.org/about-ica/about-ica-and-copper-alliance/
EU	EPC users	The International Union of Property Owners - Union Internationale de la Propriété Immobilière (UIPI ASBL)	Non-profit association of individual owners and private landlords in Europe	https://www.uipi.com/about-uipi/
				-
Austria	Companies, local communities	4ward Energy Research GmbH	Research company working on energy efficiency	https://www.4wardenergy.at/de
Germany	Municipalities	City of Maintal	municipality	https://www.maintal.de/
Germany	Municipalities	City of Eschborn	municipality	https://www.eschborn.de/
Germany	Municipalities	City of Worms	municipality	https://www.worms.de/neu-de/zukunft-gestalten/klima-und-umwelt/
Germany	Municipalities	City of Worms	municipality	https://www.worms.de/neu-de/zukunft-gestalten/klima-und-umwelt/

Germany	Municipalities	City of Nuernberg	municipality	https://www.nuernberg.de/internet/hochbauamt/projekte_energie.html
Germany	Municipalities	City of Frankfurt am Main	municipality	https://frankfurt.de/service-und-rathaus/verwaltung/aemter-und-institutionen/energiereferat
Austria	Sectoral associations (green building councils, NGOs)	Klimabündnis Steiermark	Regional association of municipalities	https://steiermark.klimabuendnis.at/
Slovenia	Energy Agencies	Sinergija Development Agency	Business development institution supporting municipalities	https://www.ra-sinergija.si/en/
Germany	Municipalities	City of Karlsruhe	municipality	https://www.karlsruhe.de/umwelt-klima/klimaschutz-klimaanpassung
Denmark	Municipalities	City of Copenhagen	municipality	https://international.kk.dk/
Czech Republic	Municipalities	City of Prague	municipality / energy community of municipality	https://prazskespolocenstvi.cz/
Spain	Public authorities	Province of Galicia	Regional Authority	https://www.xunta.gal/portada
Spain	Municipalities	Province of Gran Canaria	Regional Authority	
Spain	Municipalities	Province of Tenerife	Regional Authority	
Belgium	Companies, local communities	BASF	Chemical company	https://www.basf.com

Switzerland	Academia and research communities	École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne	Academia	https://www.epfl.ch/
Germany	Energy Agencies	Deutsche Energie-Agentur GmbH (dena) German Energy Agency	National Energy Agency	https://www.dena.de/
Germany	Regional /National certification bodies	Rheinland-Pfalz-Kreis, Building Energy Efficiency Management	Regional Authority	
Germany	Companies, local communities	ESCI gGmbH	Company	
Germany	Academia and research communities	European Climate Pact Ambassador		
Denmark	Academia and research communities	Aalborg University	Academia	
Estonia	Regional /National certification bodies	Consumer Protection and Technical Regulatory Authority	National Authority	
Estonia	Regional /National certification bodies	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications	Ministry	
Ireland	Companies, local communities	Meehan Green	Sustainability consulting services to property owners, managers, design teams and contractors	
Ireland	Academia and research communities	TU Dublin	Academia	

Ireland	Companies, local communities	RetroKit, XD Sustainable Energy Consulting Ltd	Company RetroKit supports landlords, energy upgrade professionals and one stop shops to make smart decisions for their energy renovation projects	https://retrokit.eu/
Italy	Academia and research communities	Politecnico di Milano	Academia	
Lithuania	Companies, local communities	JSC Mechanical, Electrical and Plumbing Company MEPCO	-	
Portugal	Academia and research communities	University of Coimbra	Academia	
Portugal	Energy Agencies	ADENE	Portuguese National Energy Agency	https://www.adene.pt/